

SUPPLEMENTARY

Alexander Van Uffelen

3. Benchmarking bacterial taxonomic classification using nanopore metagenomics data of several mock communities

3.1. Text

3.1.1. Commands

3.1.1.1. Kraken2 and Bracken

Kraken2 is a k-mer based classifier which classifies reads based on a lowest common ancestor (LCA) approach. Each node in the taxonomic tree of the database is assigned a weight based on the number of k-mers in the sequence associated with the taxon of the node. A k-mer gets associated with the LCA node of all organisms whose genomes contain that k-mer. Then, all root-to-leaf (RTL) paths are given a score by summing up all the weights of the nodes in the RTL path. The sequence is given the taxon of the leaf from the RTL path with the highest score. Kraken2 v2.1.1 was used with default parameters.

Bracken is a companion program to Kraken2. The reads classified by Kraken2 are converted to abundance estimates while ignoring reads at higher levels, leading to an underestimation of some species. Bracken re-estimates the species abundance by probabilistically re-distributing reads in the taxonomic tree using Bayes' theorem. Bracken v2.8 was used with the default parameters except for `-r 1000`.

3.1.1.2. Centrifuge

Centrifuge uses the memory-efficient Ferragina-Manzini (FM) index to enable rapid and accurate classification of metagenomic samples. Classification of a read begins with a short exact match that is extended until a mismatch is encountered. The taxonomic ID of the reference sequence to which the match mapped is stored. The algorithm then continues to search for other extended matches in the rest of the reads. Based on the matches, Centrifuge then scores each taxonomic ID using a certain formula. The read is classified as the taxonomic ID with the highest score. Whenever multiple taxonomic IDs have identical scores, an LCA approach is used to reduce the number of assigned taxonomic IDs by traversing the taxonomic tree to higher ranks. The number of final assigned taxonomic IDs can be changed with the parameter `-k`. This strategy differs from the LCA approach from Kraken2, which always converges to one taxonomic ID. The FM index has two advantages over k-mer based classification. Firstly, the size of the k-mer table is often large and thus requires considerable disk space. Secondly, the use of fixed k-values for k-mers imposes a tradeoff between sensitivity and precision whereas the FM-index enables the search of k-mers of any length. Centrifuge

v1.0.4 was used with default parameters except for $-k$. The parameter defines the maximum number of taxonomic labels for each read. A read can get assigned to multiple species if their assignment score is equal. If the number of assignments is higher than $-k$, Centrifuge will traverse the taxonomic tree with an LCA approach until less than $-k$ assignments remain. The parameter was set to 1 such that Centrifuge merges some of the assignments into a higher taxonomic rank until one taxonomic label is obtained. This avoids ambiguity when a read is assigned multiple taxonomic groups.

3.1.1.3. KMA

KMA is a mapping method which allows for mapping raw reads against a redundant database. The process consists out of 5 steps. Firstly, all reads are trimmed. Secondly, a heuristic k-mer mapping is applied to check whether a given sequence is eligible for further analysis. Thirdly, for all sequences that passed the heuristic mapping, the k-mers are used as seeds to extend the alignment with the Needleman-Wunsch algorithm. Fourthly, in the event of a tie for best matching reference sequences, the ConClave scoring scheme is used which favors reference sequences with more matches to be selected as best match. Lastly, a consensus sequence for a given reference sequence is made out of all the query sequences mapping to the reference. KMA v1.3.28 was used with the parameters `-mrs 0.0, -bcNano, -bc 0.7, -ef, -a, -mem_mode, -lt1` and `-matrix`, as these parameters are recommended in the manual for genome mapping with nanopore reads. Reads were assigned the taxonomic ID of the reference sequence to which they mapped.

3.1.1.4. CCMetagen

CCMetagen is a metagenomic classification pipeline around KMA which offers additional processing and filtering of the results, including two noteworthy steps. Firstly, reads are only classified if their consensus sequence (constructed by KMA) has a minimum sequencing depth, coverage and query identity to the reference sequence. By imposing these minima, the chance of false positives is reduced. Secondly, the lowest taxonomic rank that can be assigned to a consensus sequence is determined by the sequence similarity between the consensus and the reference sequence. The default similarity threshold for each taxonomic rank is pre-defined based on large-scale analysis. CCMetagen v1.4.1 was used with all parameters except `-r RefSeq` and `-m text`.

3.1.1.5. Kaiju

Kaiju uses a modified version of the backwards search algorithm in the Burrows–Wheeler transform allowing querying large sets of sequencing reads. Before the DNA sequences can be mapped against the protein reference database, they are translated into the six possible reading frames and split in amino acid fragments at stop codons. Kaiju has two search modes to classify a read: exact and greedy. For the greedy search, the longest maximum exact match (MEM) against the reference database is

searched for amongst all the fragments. The read is assigned to the taxon of the reference with the longest MEM. If there are multiple MEMs, the taxon is determined according to their LCA. The greedy search mode also starts with a (smaller) MEM but is used as seed to extend alignment from by allowing substitutions. Each fragment is scored using a BLOSUM62 matrix and the fragment with the highest score is used to classify the read. If there are fragments with an equal score, the taxon is determined according to their LCA. The greedy search mode of Kaiju v1.9.0 was used with default parameters.

3.1.1.6. MMSeqs2

MMSeqs2 consists out of three steps. Firstly, all sequences are translated according to the six possible reading frames. Secondly, all fragments unlikely to find a taxonomic hit in later stages are rejected, i.e. fragments with fewer than three consecutive similar k-mer matches. Thirdly, a novel LCA approach called 'approximate 2bLCA' is used to classify the reads. The workflow *easy-taxonomy* of MMSeqs2 v13.45111 was used with default parameters.

3.1.1.7. MetaPhlAn3

The database release *mpa_v31_CHOCOPhlan_201901* of MetaPhlAn3 contains roughly 1.1 million unique clade-specific marker genes identified from ~99,500 bacterial and archaeal and ~500 eukaryotic reference genomes. MetaPhlAn3 maps the raw reads to the marker gene database using bowtie2 and estimates the coverage of each marker. Per clade, the average coverage is calculated using the coverages of the marker genes belonging to that clade. The relative taxonomic abundance is obtained by normalizing the clade's coverage across all detected clades. MetaPhlAn v3.0.14 was used alongside bowtie v2.4.1. Default parameters were used except `--bt2_ps 'sensitive-local'` and `--unknown_estimation`. The first parameter sets the alignment mode to local as the default is global which did not yield any results. The second parameter is added so the unknown proportion is also in the output.

3.1.1.8. mOTUs2

mOTUs2 uses phylogenetic marker gene (MG)-based operational taxonomic units (mOTUs) to classify reads. Reference genomes are grouped into species-level clusters and the MG sequences of the reference genomes are grouped based on their species-level affiliation into marker gene clusters (MGCs). An mOTU is then a group of MGCs of different MGs. These mOTUs can be either derived from reference genomes (ref-mOTUs) or from metagenomic samples (meta-mOTUs). We used database v2.6.0 which contains 11,915 ref-mOTUs based on 40 universal single-copy marker genes from more than 25,000 reference genomes. The workflow of mOTUs2 consists out of three steps. Firstly, all raw reads are mapped to MGs in the database using BWA-MEM. Secondly, the read abundance of each MGC is estimated based on the mappings of the MGs in the MGC. Lastly, the abundances of the mOTUs

are calculated by taking the median of their respective MGCs' abundance. mOTUs2 v2.6 was used alongside bwa v0.7.17 and samtools v1.17. Originally, mOTUs2 was developed to only handle short reads. However, the developers later added the ability to classify long reads by cutting the short reads into smaller pieces. Thus, the long reads were chopped into smaller reads with the command `motus prep_long`. Afterwards, `motus profile` was used with parameters `-p`, `-u`, `-e` and `-q`.

3.1.2. Employed reference database

3.1.2.1. Genomic database

On 24 February 2023, genomes from the taxonomic branches archaea, bacteria, fungi, human, protozoa and viruses were downloaded. The assembly presentation was filtered on 'full' for genomes. The assembly level was set to 'complete' for the bacteria and viruses. To increase the quantity of genomes, the assembly level for archaea, fungi, and protozoa was extended to include 'scaffold' and 'contig', since only few complete genomes were otherwise available. Additionally, since the employed database was used across various research projects not in the scope of this study, nine custom genomes were added, of which four bacteria (GCF_000238355.1, GCF_000260835.1, GCF_018967645.1, GCF_900236745.1), four fungi (GCA_900893395.1, GCA_025331445.1, GCA_028975445.1, GCA_028975465.1) and one unicellular alga (GCA_900893395.1).

3.1.2.2. Protein database

In the NCBI nr protein database, all identical sequences are merged into one entry. Consequently, each sequence in the database is unique but can originate from distinct organisms. For consistency, the same taxonomic filtering was applied as in the RefSeq database, i.e., proteins belonging to the taxonomic branches archaea, bacteria, fungi, human, protozoa, and viruses. On 5 September 2022, proteins from those respective taxonomic branches were extracted using `blastdbcmd/2.13.01`. Protozoa do not correspond to a separate branch in the NCBI taxonomic database, although it is a separate taxonomic branch in RefSeq. A set of taxonomic IDs derived from the protozoan assemblies in RefSeq was therefore used. A Lowest Common Ancestor (LCA) approach was used to assign one taxonomic ID to each protein sequence since entries in the nr protein database could originate from different organisms. As a final processing step, all proteins with non-canonical amino acids (i.e., B, J, O, U, Z, and X) were removed from the database because not all classifiers could handle these non-canonical amino acids.

3.1.2.3. Taxonomic IDs

During classification, each sequence read gets assigned a taxonomic ID dependent on matching in the reference database. These taxonomic IDs originate from the NCBI Taxonomy database and are subject

to continuous change as new taxa are added². Consequently, taxonomic IDs may undergo merging or deletion. Likewise, taxonomic names may change due to synonyms, misspellings, etc. The volatility of taxonomic IDs and names poses a problem when comparing the ground truth of the mock communities with the output of the different classifiers. Because the output of a classifier depends on the taxonomy files used to build the classifier's database and because the taxonomy files change over time, comparing the ground truth and the output of the classifier can lead to incorrect conclusions (see Figure S3.17). However, NCBI tracks merged and deleted taxonomic IDs alongside the current taxonomic IDs and names. This information is available in the taxonomy dump files on the NCBI ftp server. Using the same taxonomy dump files to update the taxonomic IDs obtained on different dates solves the problem of merging taxonomic IDs. Additionally, translating the updated taxonomic IDs into taxonomic names (using again the same taxonomy dump files) ensures that the same taxonomic IDs result in the same taxonomic names. Taxonkit v0.13.0³ was used to update the taxonomic IDs of the ground truth and classifiers' output. Taxonomic IDs that were merged were updated to their new taxonomic ID, and deleted taxonomic IDs were flagged. Afterwards, the taxonomic IDs were converted to their genus and species name. In case a certain taxonomic ID had a species rank, but not genus rank, the taxonomic name of the genus was converted to 'missing_genus'. These names were used to compare the output of the classifiers to the ground truth.

3.1.3. Metric formulas

$$\frac{S_i}{T_i} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{R_i}{(L_i P_i)}}{\sum_{i=1}^n R_i} * L_i P_i$$

where S_i is the sequence abundance, T_i is the taxonomic abundance, R_i is the number of reads, L_i is the genome length, and P_i is the ploidy of taxon i . Because L_i and P_i vary across different taxa, S_i and T_i are not connected by any universal or sample-independent algebraic relation. However, the taxa in the DMCs are known. Consequently, L_i can be determined through the representative genome on NCBI for every taxon. Regarding ploidy P_i , a value of 1 was used for prokaryotes and a value of 2 for eukaryotes.

3.1.4. Performance evaluation of the different taxonomic classifiers at genus level

3.1.4.1. DNA-to-DNA methods

At genus level, many of the same trends as observed at species level were apparent (Figure S3.11). The median precision of KMA (0.486) increased substantially while the median precision of Kraken2

(0.048) and Centrifuge (0.025) stayed low. The median recall for Kraken2, KMA and Centrifuge for all datasets was 1 except for the three StrainMad and Zymo_D6331 datasets for which KMA scored less than Kraken2 and Centrifuge. Nevertheless, the median F1 score of KMA (0.654) was much higher compared to Kraken2 (0.092) and Centrifuge (0.049). The median L1 distances at genus level were lower than at species level, but again very similar with median values of 0.554, 0.564 and 0.572 for Kraken2, KMA and Centrifuge, respectively. CCMetagen's precision (0.971) and recall (0.706) increased, still being the highest and lowest, respectively, resulting in the highest F1 score (0.782). Similar to the species level, Bracken did not substantially change the relative abundance estimates of Kraken2.

3.1.4.2. DNA-to-protein methods

At genus level, the same trends as at species level were apparent (Figure S3.11). The precision of MMSeqs2 (0.125) was still higher than Kaiju's precision (0.036). The difference in recall between Kaiju and MMSeqs2 was less pronounced. While Kaiju retained a median recall of 1, the median recall of MMSeqs2 also increased to 1. Furthermore, MMSeqs2 had only two datasets with a slightly lower recall than Kaiju, compared to five datasets at species level. The difference in median F1 score increased between Kaiju (0.069) and MMSeqs2 (0.222). The median L1 distance of Kaiju (0.689) approached that of DNA-to-DNA classifiers while the L1 distance of MMSeqs2 (0.825) remained the highest.

3.1.4.3. DNA-to-marker methods

At genus level, the median precision of MetaPhlAn3 (0.556) increased. The median precision of mOTUs2 remained 1, but surprisingly the precision of two datasets decreased. This decline can be attributed to certain mOTUs encompassing multiple species. In such instances, these mOTUs are labeled as 'unclassified' at species level but are still included at genus level, akin to a lowest common ancestor approach. Consequently, this could potentially lead to false positives at the genus level while maintaining precision at the species level, resulting in an overall lower precision at the genus level. The median recall of both classifiers increased, but the difference between MetaPhlAn3 (0.702) and mOTUs2 (0.647) became more pronounced. The F1 score of MetaPhlAn3 (0.684) increased substantially compared to the marginal increase of mOTUs2 (0.759). Noteworthy, while mOTUs2 had the highest median F1 score of all classifiers at the species level, CCMetagen's median F1 score was the highest at genus level. The difference in the median L1 distance was less pronounced with for both MetaPhlAn3 (0.652) and for mOTUs2 (0.524).

3.1.4.4. Area under the precision-recall curve

At genus level, all classifiers had an increased median AUPRC with the exception of a marginal decrease for mOTUs2 compared to the species level (Figure S3.11). Both DNA-to-marker methods, MetaPhlan3 (0.687) and mOTUS2 (0.596), still had the lowest median AUPRC. Remarkably, DNA-to-protein methods, Kaiju (0.940) and MMSeqs2 (0.942), experienced the highest increase in AUPRC and as a consequence had higher AUPRC scores than the other classifiers. For DNA-to-DNA methods, the median AUPRC for Kraken2 (0.919), Bracken (0.919), KMA (0.935), Centrifuge (0.890) and CCMetagen (0.654) increased. While CCMetagen's AUPRC value was the lowest at species level, the median AUPRC of mOTUs2 became the lowest at genus level.

3.1.4.5. Effect of abundance filtering on precision, recall and F1

At genus level, the trends of precision, recall and F1 at varying thresholds between the different classifiers were similar as at species level but less pronounced (Figure S3.14). Additionally, the spread of the IQRs and the minimum/maximum values were lower. The maximum precision of DNA-to-DNA methods, including CCMetagen, was reached very quickly at a low threshold except for Centrifuge, which reached this at a higher threshold. KMA and CCMetagen were able to reach a maximum precision of 1, which they could not achieve at species level. The slope of the recall followed a similar course as at species level with the steepest descent before a threshold of 0.1%. Because the maximum precision was higher and the recall followed the same pace, a higher maximum F1 score was reached with, and for Kraken2 (0.846), Bracken (0.838), KMA (0.903) and Centrifuge (0.843). As at species level, a filtering threshold of 0.05% appeared well-balanced for these methods. For CCMetagen, the highest F1 score was reached without filtering. Although the increase of precision for DNA-to-protein methods at genus level was still slower than DNA-to-DNA methods, their maximum precision was reached faster than at species level. Again, the slope of the recall followed a similar course as at species level with the steepest descent before a threshold of 0.15%. Consequently, similar to DNA-to-DNA methods, their maximum median F1 score was higher and reached faster. Kaiju (0.804) and MMSeqs2 (0.800) reached a maximum median F1 score at 0.2% and 0.05%, respectively. Therefore, less strict filtering than at species level was required with 0.05% appearing a well-balanced cutoff. Lastly, for both DNA-to-markers methods, their maximum F1 score was also higher and reached faster with 0.725 at 0.2% for MetaPhlan3, and 0.759 without filtering for mOTUs2. Since the F1 score for MetaPhlan3 decreased, and the F1 score of mOTUs2 remained constant before a filtering threshold of 0.1%, it appeared no additional filtering is recommended for these methods at genus level.

3.1.4.6. Assessment of overall classifier performance

A summary of precision and recall of all classifiers at genus level is displayed in Figure S3.15A. The same three groups as at species level were apparent but less pronounced due to a substantial improvement of KMA's precision, which was comparable to MetaPhlan3's precision. For the first group, recall values were less spread out and MMSeqs2 reached a median recall of 1. The second group, i.e., MetaPhlan3, had a notably improved precision and a higher IQR for recall. The third group did not change much, except for a slightly higher recall for both CCMetagen and mOTUs2, resulting in CCMetagen having a higher median recall than mOTUs2. Figures S3.15B and S3.15C show the transition of the recall and precision as error bars after applying filter thresholds of 0.05% and 0.1%, respectively. The first group's recall decreased less and its precision improved more than at species level. For the second group, the change in precision and recall was very similar to the change at species level with only an increase in precision at a threshold of 0.1% and a small decrease in recall for both thresholds. For the third group, the filtering hardly made a difference, except for a small improvement of the median precision and a decrease in recall for CCMetagen. Coupled with the filtering effect on F1 values (Figure S3.14), recommended threshold values of 0.05% were therefore advised for the first group, and no filtering for the second and third group.

3.1.5. Evaluation of classification performance using a single ONT R10 DMC at genus level

Figure S3.16 presents results for classification performance of all classifiers compared to the R9 and R10 datasets of sample Zymo D6322 at genus level. At species level, only CCMetagen showed a substantial shift in absolute precision, whereas at genus level KMA (0.072), CCMetagen (-0.111) and MetaPhlan3 (0.061) all displayed notable change. In relative precision, the difference at genus level between the R9 and R10 dataset followed a similar trajectory as observed at species level, albeit with a larger magnitude of change. The relative precision decreased for CCMetagen (-11.11%), Centrifuge (-23.50%) and MMseqs2 (-17.92%); and increased for Kraken2/Bracken (+5.26%), KMA (+26.09%), Kaiju (+25.14%), and MetaPhlan3 (+19.05%). The precision of mOTUs2 remained the same in both datasets. In contrast, there were no differences in FNs between the R9 and R10 datasets so that the recall for all classifiers remained the same. Consequently, F1 score differences between the R9 and R10 datasets mirrored trends observed for precision with the R10 dataset showing a relative F1 score decrease for CCMetagen (-5.88%), Centrifuge (-23.14%), and MMseqs2 (-16.67%); a relative F1 score increase for Kraken2/Bracken (4.85%), KMA (19.36%), Kaiju (24.06%), and MetaPhlan3 (13.79%); and the same F1 score for mOTUs2.

3.2. Figures

Figure S3.1

Figure S3.1: A scatter plot of the reads for Zymo D6322 R9. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.2

Figure S3.2: A scatter plot of the reads for Zymo D6322 R10. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.3

Figure S3.3: A scatter plot of the reads for BEI HM-276D. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.4

Figure S3.4: A scatter plot of the reads for BEI HM-277D. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.5

Figure S3.5: A scatter plot of the reads for Strain Madness 1. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.6

Figure S3.6: A scatter plot of the reads for Strain Madness 2. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.7

Figure S3.7: A scatter plot of the reads for Strain Madness 3. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.8

Figure S3.8: A scatter plot of the reads for Zymo D6300. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.9

Figure S3.9: A scatter plot of the reads for Zymo D6310. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.10

Figure S3.10: A scatter plot of the reads for Zymo D6331. The x-axis represents the length while the y-axis represents the mean quality of each read. The histograms of the length and quality are shown at the top and right side, respectively. A random subsample of 100,000 reads is plotted.

Figure S3.11

Figure S3.11: Performance evaluation for the different classifiers aggregated over all DMCs at genus level. Each subplot represents a performance metric with panels a, b, c, d and e showing precision, recall, F1, L1, and AUPRC, respectively. For each subplot, the y-axis displays the metric value and the x-axis the different classifiers. For every classifier, the metric values of all datasets are summarized in a boxplot with the median value as horizontal line, upon which superimposed individual dots represent specific values for the different DMCs (dots can be superimposed upon each other if the same

value was observed). Outliers are denoted by dots enclosed in a black circle. The legend in the lower right panel corresponds to the DMC identifiers presented in Table 1.

1 Figure S3.12

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3 Figure S3.12: Precision, recall and F1 when filtering is applied at species level. The first, second and third plot show the median precision, recall and F1 scores, respectively, for the different
4 classifier over various threshold filters.

5 Figure S3.13

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7 Figure S3.13: Precision, recall and F1 when filtering is applied at genus level. The first, second and third plot show the median precision, recall and F1 scores, respectively, for the different
8 classifier over various threshold filters.

9 Figure S3.14

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11 Figure S3.14: Precision, recall and F1 for the different classifiers when filtering is applied at genus level. The first, second and third row represent precision, recall and F1 score, respectively,
 12 and each column displays a different classifier. The x-axis of every subplot represents the applied filter threshold for which all species below this threshold were considered as a negative, and
 13 the y-axis displays the metric value. Each subplot contains three shades of color with the darkest shade showing the median, the medium shade showing the IQR, and the lightest shade
 14 showing the minimum/maximum values over all DMCS.

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18 Figure S3.15: Overall median precision and recall values at genus level for the different classifiers. The dots in panel a represent the median precision (x-axis) and recall (y-axis) values for
 19 every classifier aggregated over all DMCs, while the error bars indicate the extent of the IQR for both the precision and the recall. The dots in panels b and c similarly indicate median precision
 20 (x-axis) and recall (y-axis) values for every classifier aggregated over all DMCs, but with error flags indicating the updated median precision and recall for an abundance filtering threshold of
 21 0.05% and 0.1%, respectively.

23

24 Figure S3.16: Precision, recall and F1 values at genus level for the R9 and R10 dataset of Zymo D6322. The dots in panel A,
 25 B and C represent the precision, recall and F1 values (left axis), respectively, for every classifier of both the R9 dataset and
 26 R10 dataset of the DMC Zymo D6322. Dots can be superimposed upon each other if (nearly) identical values were
 27 observed. The bars in each panel present the percentage change (right axis) from the R9 to R10 metric value.

28 Figure S3.17

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30 Figure S3.17: Comparing two tax IDs obtained at different dates can result in a faulty conclusion due to changes in
31 taxonomic ID. A) Tax ID 1 from the ground truth and tax ID 2 from the reference database point to the same species but
32 have a different taxonomic ID due to being collected at a different point in time. Comparing the two tax IDs can therefore
33 lead to the faulty conclusion of being different species. B) Because NCBI keeps track of merged and deleted tax IDs,
34 Taxonkit can be used to update tax IDs so the ground truth and the output of the classifier will be the same if the
35 species/genus is the same.

36

	Starting materia l	Taxid	Super kingdom	Species	Relative abundance
Bei Resources HM-276D	DNA	470	Bacteria	Acinetobacter baumannii	0.04815
		1396	Bacteria	Bacillus cereus	0.03163
		1063	Bacteria	Cereibacter sphaeroides	0.10004
		1520	Bacteria	Clostridium beijerinckii	0.03114
		1747	Bacteria	Cutibacterium acnes	0.062
		1299	Bacteria	Deinococcus radiodurans	0.07412
		1351	Bacteria	Enterococcus faecalis	0.04975
		562	Bacteria	Escherichia coli	0.04817
		210	Bacteria	Helicobacter pylori	0.06058
		1596	Bacteria	Lactobacillus gasseri	0.02294
		1639	Bacteria	Listeria monocytogenes	0.03565
		487	Bacteria	Neisseria meningitidis	0.04127
		821	Bacteria	Phocaeicola vulgatus	0.05358
		287	Bacteria	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	0.11377
		1660	Bacteria	Schaalia odontolytica	0.05796
		1280	Bacteria	Staphylococcus aureus	0.04174
		1282	Bacteria	Staphylococcus epidermidis	0.03631
		1311	Bacteria	Streptococcus agalactiae	0.02242
		1309	Bacteria	Streptococcus mutans	0.02954
		1313	Bacteria	Streptococcus pneumoniae	0.03924

Bei Resources HM-277D	DNA	470	Bacteria	Acinetobacter baumannii	NA
		1396	Bacteria	Bacillus cereus	NA
		1063	Bacteria	Cereibacter sphaeroides	NA

		1520	Bacteria	Clostridium beijerinckii	NA
		1747	Bacteria	Cutibacterium acnes	NA
		1299	Bacteria	Deinococcus radiodurans	NA
		1351	Bacteria	Enterococcus faecalis	NA
		562	Bacteria	Escherichia coli	NA
		210	Bacteria	Helicobacter pylori	NA
		1596	Bacteria	Lactobacillus gasseri	NA
		1639	Bacteria	Listeria monocytogenes	NA
		487	Bacteria	Neisseria meningitidis	NA
		821	Bacteria	Phocaeicola vulgatus	NA
		287	Bacteria	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	NA
		1660	Bacteria	Schaalia odontolytica	NA
		1280	Bacteria	Staphylococcus aureus	NA
		1282	Bacteria	Staphylococcus epidermidis	NA
		1311	Bacteria	Streptococcus agalactiae	NA
		1309	Bacteria	Streptococcus mutans	NA
		1313	Bacteria	Streptococcus pneumoniae	NA

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Strain Madness 1	DNA and cells	242703	Archaea	Acidilobus saccharovorans	0.0003
		2234	Archaea	Archaeoglobus fulgidus	0.0117

		379547	Archaea	Candidatus Aciduliprofundum boonei	0.0003
		2242	Archaea	Halobacterium salinarum	0.0253
		2246	Archaea	Haloferax volcanii	0.0005
		160233	Archaea	Ignicoccus hospitalis	0.0284
		54259	Archaea	Ignicoccus islandicus	0.011
		66851	Archaea	Methanobrevibacter oralis	0.0076
		2190	Archaea	Methanocaldococcus jannaschii	0.0565
		39152	Archaea	Methanococcus maripaludis	0.0161
		1080712	Archaea	Methanomassiliicoccus luminyensis	0.0006
		101192	Archaea	Methanomethylovorans hollandica	0.0005
		2320	Archaea	Methanopyrus kandleri	0.0021
		2214	Archaea	Methanosarcina acetivorans	0.0018
		2180	Archaea	Methanothermus fervidus	0.0718
		160232	Archaea	Nanoarchaeum equitans	0.0096
		13773	Archaea	Pyrobaculum aerophilum	0.0023
		121277	Archaea	Pyrobaculum arsenaticum	0.0005
		181486	Archaea	Pyrobaculum caldifontis	0.0254

		2261	Archaea	Pyrococcus furiosus	0.004
		53953	Archaea	Pyrococcus horikoshii	0.0586
		111955	Archaea	Sulfurisphaera tokodaii	0.0008
		1515	Bacteria	Acetivibrio thermocellus	0.0027
		33075	Bacteria	Acidobacterium capsulatum	0.002
		239935	Bacteria	Akkermansia muciniphila	0.0091
		818	Bacteria	Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron	0.0032
		520	Bacteria	Bordetella pertussis	0.0048
		31899	Bacteria	Caldicellulosiruptor bescii	0.0021
		44001	Bacteria	Caldicellulosiruptor saccharolyticus	0.0089
		1097	Bacteria	Chlorobaculum tepidum	0.0024
		1092	Bacteria	Chlorobium limicola	0.0232
		1096	Bacteria	Chlorobium phaeobacteroides	0.0069
		1094	Bacteria	Chlorobium phaeovibrioides	0.0129
		1108	Bacteria	Chloroflexus aurantiacus	0.002
		225194	Bacteria	Citri fermentans bemidjiense	0.000033
		1299	Bacteria	Deinococcus radiodurans	0.0062

		36854	Bacteria	Desulfitobacterium dehalogenans	0.000033
		1986146	Bacteria	Desulfobulbus oralis	0.0735
		901	Bacteria	Desulfovibrio piger	0.0439
		881	Bacteria	Desulfovibrio vulgaris	0.0003
		513050	Bacteria	Dictyoglomus turgidum	0.0069
		1351	Bacteria	Enterococcus faecalis	0.0015
		851	Bacteria	Fusobacterium nucleatum	0.0281
		173480	Bacteria	Gemmatimonas aurantiaca	0.0241
		35554	Bacteria	Geobacter sulfurreducens	0.0059
		65	Bacteria	Herpetosiphon aurantiacus	0.0165
		380749	Bacteria	Hydrogenobaculum sp. Y04AAS1	0.0163
		34029	Bacteria	Leptothrix cholodnii	0.0005
		915	Bacteria	Nitrosomonas europaea	0.0568
		103690	Bacteria	Nostoc sp. PCC 7120 = FACHB-418	0.0137
		36873	Bacteria	Paraburkholderia xenovorans	0.0058
		309805	Bacteria	Persephonella marina	0.0281
		821	Bacteria	Phocaeicola vulgatus	0.0047

		837	Bacteria	Porphyromonas gingivalis	0.0217
		641491	Bacteria	Pseudodesulfovibrio mercurii	0.0005
		294	Bacteria	Pseudomonas fluorescens	0.0107
		303	Bacteria	Pseudomonas putida	0.0148
		265606	Bacteria	Rhodopirellula baltica	0.0132
		89184	Bacteria	Ruegeria pomeroyi	0.0007
		168697	Bacteria	Salinispora arenicola	0.0039
		168695	Bacteria	Salinispora tropica	0.0049
		62322	Bacteria	Shewanella baltica	0.039
		359303	Bacteria	Shewanella loihica	0.0055
		436114	Bacteria	Sulfurihydrogenibium sp. YO3AOP1	0.0069
		496866	Bacteria	Thermoanaerobacter pseudethanolicus	0.0248
		2337	Bacteria	Thermotoga neapolitana	0.0161
		93929	Bacteria	Thermotoga petrophila	0.0695
		158	Bacteria	Treponema denticola	0.0127
		844	Bacteria	Wolinella succinogenes	0.0066

41

Strain Madness 2		242703	Archaea	Acidilobus saccharovorans	0.0003
		2234	Archaea	Archaeoglobus fulgidus	0.0115

DNA and cells	379547	Archaea	Candidatus Aciduliprofundum boonei	0.0003
	2242	Archaea	Halobacterium salinarum	0.025
	2246	Archaea	Haloferax volcanii	0.0005
	160233	Archaea	Ignicoccus hospitalis	0.028
	54259	Archaea	Ignicoccus islandicus	0.0108
	66851	Archaea	Methanobrevibacter oralis	0.0075
	2190	Archaea	Methanocaldococcus jannaschii	0.0557
	39152	Archaea	Methanococcus maripaludis	0.0159
	1080712	Archaea	Methanomassiliicoccus luminyensis	0.0006
	101192	Archaea	Methanomethylovorans hollandica	0.0005
	2320	Archaea	Methanopyrus kandleri	0.0021
	2214	Archaea	Methanosarcina acetivorans	0.0017
	2180	Archaea	Methanothermus fervidus	0.0708
	160232	Archaea	Nanoarchaeum equitans	0.0094
	13773	Archaea	Pyrobaculum aerophilum	0.0023
121277	Archaea	Pyrobaculum arsenaticum	0.0005	
181486	Archaea	Pyrobaculum caldifontis	0.0251	

		2261	Archaea	Pyrococcus furiosus	0.004
		53953	Archaea	Pyrococcus horikoshii	0.0577
		111955	Archaea	Sulfurisphaera tokodaii	0.0007
		1515	Bacteria	Acetivibrio thermocellus	0.0027
		33075	Bacteria	Acidobacterium capsulatum	0.002
		470	Bacteria	Acinetobacter baumannii	0.0005
		239935	Bacteria	Akkermansia muciniphila	0.0089
		1396	Bacteria	Bacillus cereus	0.0004
		818	Bacteria	Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron	0.0032
		1680	Bacteria	Bifidobacterium adolescentis	0.001
		520	Bacteria	Bordetella pertussis	0.0047
		31899	Bacteria	Caldicellulosiruptor bescii	0.0021
		44001	Bacteria	Caldicellulosiruptor saccharolyticus	0.0088
		1063	Bacteria	Cereibacter sphaeroides	0.0004
		1097	Bacteria	Chlorobaculum tepidum	0.0024
		1092	Bacteria	Chlorobium limicola	0.0229
		1096	Bacteria	Chlorobium phaeobacteroides	0.0068

		1094	Bacteria	Chlorobium phaeovibrioides	0.0128
		225194	Bacteria	Citrifermentans bemidjiense	0.000033
		1108	Bacteria	Chloroflexus aurantiacus	0.002
		1520	Bacteria	Clostridium beijerinckii	0.0003
		1747	Bacteria	Cutibacterium acnes	0.0008
		1299	Bacteria	Deinococcus radiodurans	0.0067
		36854	Bacteria	Desulfitobacterium dehalogenans	0.000033
		1986146	Bacteria	Desulfobulbus oralis	0.0725
		901	Bacteria	Desulfovibrio piger	0.0433
		881	Bacteria	Desulfovibrio vulgaris	0.0003
		513050	Bacteria	Dictyoglomus turgidum	0.0068
		1351	Bacteria	Enterococcus faecalis	0.0021
		562	Bacteria	Escherichia coli	0.0004
		851	Bacteria	Fusobacterium nucleatum	0.0277
		173480	Bacteria	Gemmatimonas aurantiaca	0.0238
		35554	Bacteria	Geobacter sulfurreducens	0.0058
		210	Bacteria	Helicobacter pylori	0.0012
		65	Bacteria	Herpetosiphon aurantiacus	0.0163

		380749	Bacteria	Hydrogenobaculum sp. Y04AAS1	0.0161
		1596	Bacteria	Lactobacillus gasseri	0.0011
		34029	Bacteria	Leptothrix cholodnii	0.0005
		487	Bacteria	Neisseria meningitidis	0.0009
		915	Bacteria	Nitrosomonas europaea	0.056
		103690	Bacteria	Nostoc sp. PCC 7120 = FACHB-418	0.0135
		36873	Bacteria	Paraburkholderia xenovorans	0.0057
		309805	Bacteria	Persephonella marina	0.0277
		821	Bacteria	Phocaeicola vulgatus	0.005
		837	Bacteria	Porphyromonas gingivalis	0.0223
		641491	Bacteria	Pseudodesulfovibrio mercurii	0.0005
		294	Bacteria	Pseudomonas fluorescens	0.0105
		2994495	Bacteria	Pseudomonas paraeruginosa	0.0003
		303	Bacteria	Pseudomonas putida	0.0146
		265606	Bacteria	Rhodopirellula baltica	0.013
		89184	Bacteria	Ruegeria pomeroyi	0.0007
		168697	Bacteria	Salinispora arenicola	0.0039
		168695	Bacteria	Salinispora tropica	0.0048

		1660	Bacteria	Schaalia odontolytica	0.0008
		62322	Bacteria	Shewanella baltica	0.0384
		359303	Bacteria	Shewanella loihica	0.0055
		1280	Bacteria	Staphylococcus aureus	0.0007
		1282	Bacteria	Staphylococcus epidermidis	0.0008
		1311	Bacteria	Streptococcus agalactiae	0.0009
		1309	Bacteria	Streptococcus mutans	0.001
		436114	Bacteria	Sulfurihydrogenibium sp. YO3AOP1	0.0068
		496866	Bacteria	Thermoanaerobacter pseudethanolicus	0.0245
		2337	Bacteria	Thermotoga neapolitana	0.0158
		93929	Bacteria	Thermotoga petrophila	0.0685
		158	Bacteria	Treponema denticola	0.0125
		844	Bacteria	Wolinella succinogenes	0.0065

42

Strain Madness 3	DNA and cells	242703	Archaea	Acidilobus saccharovorans	0.0003
		2234	Archaea	Archaeoglobus fulgidus	0.0092
		2242	Archaea	Halobacterium salinarum	0.0249
		2246	Archaea	Halof erax volcanii	0.0005
		160233	Archaea	Ignicoccus hospitalis	0.0419

		54259	Archaea	Ignicoccus islandicus	0.027
		2190	Archaea	Methanocaldococcus jannaschii	0.1112
		39152	Archaea	Methanococcus maripaludis	0.0144
		2320	Archaea	Methanopyrus kandleri	0.0026
		2214	Archaea	Methanosarcina acetivorans	0.0017
		2180	Archaea	Methanothermus fervidus	0.0566
		160232	Archaea	Nanoarchaeum equitans	0.0062
		13773	Archaea	Pyrobaculum aerophilum	0.0011
		181486	Archaea	Pyrobaculum caldifontis	0.005
		53953	Archaea	Pyrococcus horikoshii	0.0721
		111955	Archaea	Sulfurisphaera tokodaii	0.0007
		1515	Bacteria	Acetivibrio thermocellus	0.0016
		33075	Bacteria	Acidobacterium capsulatum	0.0012
		239935	Bacteria	Akkermansia muciniphila	0.0125
		818	Bacteria	Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron	0.002
		520	Bacteria	Bordetella pertussis	0.0047
		31899	Bacteria	Caldicellulosiruptor bescii	0.0021

		44001	Bacteria	Caldicellulosiruptor saccharolyticus	0.0132
		1097	Bacteria	Chlorobaculum tepidum	0.006
		1092	Bacteria	Chlorobium limicola	0.0137
		1096	Bacteria	Chlorobium phaeobacteroides	0.0068
		1094	Bacteria	Chlorobium phaeovibrioides	0.0191
		1108	Bacteria	Chloroflexus aurantiacus	0.001
		1299	Bacteria	Deinococcus radiodurans	0.0046
		1986146	Bacteria	Desulfobulbus oralis	0.0362
		899	Bacteria	Desulfomicrobium baculatum	0.0004
		901	Bacteria	Desulfovibrio piger	0.0648
		881	Bacteria	Desulfovibrio vulgaris	0.0005
		513050	Bacteria	Dictyoglomus turgidum	0.0054
		1351	Bacteria	Enterococcus faecalis	0.003
		851	Bacteria	Fusobacterium nucleatum	0.0138
		173480	Bacteria	Gemmatimonas aurantiaca	0.0238
		35554	Bacteria	Geobacter sulfurreducens	0.001
		65	Bacteria	Herpetosiphon aurantiacus	0.026

		380749	Bacteria	Hydrogenobaculum sp. Y04AAS1	0.0129
		915	Bacteria	Nitrosomonas europaea	0.028
		103690	Bacteria	Nostoc sp. PCC 7120 = FACHB-418	0.0203
		36873	Bacteria	Paraburkholderia xenovorans	0.0028
		34090	Bacteria	Pelodictyon phaeoclathratiforme	0.001
		309805	Bacteria	Persephonella marina	0.0152
		821	Bacteria	Phocaeicola vulgatus	0.0139
		837	Bacteria	Porphyromonas gingivalis	0.0427
		641491	Bacteria	Pseudodesulfovibrio mercurii	0.0003
		294	Bacteria	Pseudomonas fluorescens	0.0035
		303	Bacteria	Pseudomonas putida	0.0118
		265606	Bacteria	Rhodopirellula baltica	0.0078
		168697	Bacteria	Salinispora arenicola	0.0031
		168695	Bacteria	Salinispora tropica	0.0039
		62322	Bacteria	Shewanella baltica	0.0478
		359303	Bacteria	Shewanella loihica	0.0076
		436114	Bacteria	Sulfurihydrogenibium sp. YO3AOP1	0.0055

		496866	Bacteria	Thermoanaerobacter pseudethanolicus	0.0183
		2336	Bacteria	Thermotoga maritima	0.0614
		2337	Bacteria	Thermotoga neapolitana	0.0317
		158	Bacteria	Treponema denticola	0.0156
		844	Bacteria	Wolinella succinogenes	0.0054
		542	Bacteria	Zymomonas mobilis	0.0005

43

Zymo D6300	Cells	1423	Bacteria	Bacillus subtilis	0.12
		1351	Bacteria	Enterococcus faecalis	0.12
		562	Bacteria	Escherichia coli	0.12
		1613	Bacteria	Limosilactobacillus fermentum	0.12
		1639	Bacteria	Listeria monocytogenes	0.12
		287	Bacteria	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	0.12
		28901	Bacteria	Salmonella enterica	0.12
		1280	Bacteria	Staphylococcus aureus	0.12
		5207	Eukaryota	Cryptococcus neoformans	0.02
		4932	Eukaryota	Saccharomyces cerevisiae	0.02

44

Zymo D6310	Cells	1423	Bacteria	Bacillus subtilis	0.0089
		1351	Bacteria	Enterococcus faecalis	0.0000089

		562	Bacteria	Escherichia coli	0.00089
		1613	Bacteria	Limosilactobacillus fermentum	0.000089
		1639	Bacteria	Listeria monocytogenes	0.891
		287	Bacteria	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	0.08900000
		28901	Bacteria	Salmonella enterica	0.00089
		1280	Bacteria	Staphylococcus aureus	0.00000089
		5207	Eukaryota	Cryptococcus neoformans	0.0000089
		4932	Eukaryota	Saccharomyces cerevisiae	0.0089

45

Zymo D6322	DNA	1423	Bacteria	Bacillus subtilis	0.14
		1351	Bacteria	Enterococcus faecalis	0.14
		562	Bacteria	Escherichia coli	0.14
		1639	Bacteria	Listeria monocytogenes	0.14
		287	Bacteria	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	0.14
		28901	Bacteria	Salmonella enterica	0.14
		1280	Bacteria	Staphylococcus aureus	0.14
		4932	Eukaryota	Saccharomyces cerevisiae	0.02

46

Zymo D6331	Cells	2173	Archaea	Methanobrevibacter smithii	0.001
		239935	Bacteria	Akkermansia muciniphila	0.015

		817	Bacteria	Bacteroides fragilis	0.14
		1680	Bacteria	Bifidobacterium adolescentis	0.06
		1496	Bacteria	Clostridioides difficile	0.015
		1502	Bacteria	Clostridium perfringens	0.000001
		1351	Bacteria	Enterococcus faecalis	0.00001
		562	Bacteria	Escherichia coli	0.14
		853	Bacteria	Faecalibacterium prausnitzii	0.14
		851	Bacteria	Fusobacterium nucleatum	0.06
		1613	Bacteria	Limosilactobacillus fermentum	0.06
		28128	Bacteria	Prevotella corporis	0.06
		301301	Bacteria	Roseburia hominis	0.14
		28901	Bacteria	Salmonella enterica	0.0001
		423477	Bacteria	Veillonella rogosae	0.14
		5476	Eukaryota	Candida albicans	0.015
		4932	Eukaryota	Saccharomyces cerevisiae	0.014

47 Table S3.1: Composition of each DMC. The first column lists the name of each DMC. The second column states whether the
48 DMC was originally available as cells or DNA. The third column displays the taxonomic ID of the present organism. The
49 fourth and fifth column shows the superkingdom and species. The last column shows the relative abundance of each
50 organism.

51

52

54 Table S3.2

GENUS	DMC	Genomic	Protein	Marker mOTU	Marker Metaphlan
	Zymo Research D6300	10/10	10/10	8/10	10/10
	Zymo Research D6310	10/10	10/10	8/10	10/10
	Zymo Research D6322	8/8	8/8	7/8	8/8
	Zymo Research D6331	17/17	17/17	15/17	17/17
	Bei Resources HM-276D	17/17	17/17	17/17	17/17
	Bei Resources HM-277D	17/17	17/17	17/17	17/17
	Sevim, V., Lee, J., Egan, R. et al.	55/57	57/57	57/57	56/57
		68/70	70/70	70/70	69/70
50/52		52/52	52/52	51/52	

55

SPECIES	DMC	Genomic	Protein	Marker mOTUs2	Marker Metaphlan3
	Zymo Research D6300	10/10	10/10	8/10	8/10
	Zymo Research D6310	10/10	10/10	8/10	8/10
	Zymo Research D6322	8/8	8/8	7/8	6/8
	Zymo Research D6331	17/17	17/17	15/17	17/17
	Bei Resources HM-276D	20/20	20/20	18/20	18/20
	Bei Resources HM-277D	20/20	20/20	18/20	18/20
	Sevim, V., Lee, J., Egan, R. et al.	63/69	69/69	62/69	62/69
		79/85	84/85	76/85	76/85
55/62		60/62	55/62	56/62	

56 **Table S3.2: The number of present genera and species in the databases for every DMC.** For each sample (row) and
57 database (column), a fraction is displayed. The first table and second table show fractions for the genera and the species,
58 respectively, in the samples and databases. The denominator displays the number of genera/species in the ground truth
59 for the DMC. The nominator shows the number of genera/species from the ground truth that is also contained in the
60 database. The fraction equals the maximum recall that can be achieved by the classifier types for a certain DMC.

61

62 Table S3.3

DMC	Kraken2	KMA	Centrifuge	Kaiju	MMSeqs2	Metaphlan3	mOTUs2
Zymo Research D6300	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	2-2	2-2
Zymo Research D6310	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	1-0	9-2	7-2
Zymo Research D6322	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	2-2	1-1
Zymo Research D6331	1-0	1-0	1-0	1-0	2-0	4-0	6-2
Bei Resources HM-276D	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	3-2	4-2
Bei Resources HM-277D	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	0-0	9-2	8-2
Strain Madness 1	7-6	8-6	6-6	3-0	7-0	24-7	33-7
Strain Madness 2	7-6	8-6	6-6	4-1	14-1	40-9	48-9
Strain Madness 3	5-5	7-5	5-5	2-0	8-0	22-6	29-7
TOTAL	3	7	1	9	31	83	104

63 Table S3.3: Each cell represent for every DMC and classifier the subtraction of the number of FNs and the number of
64 missing species in the database. For every dataset (row) and classifier (column), the first number in the equation represent
65 the number of FNs for a certain DMC and classifier. The number after the subtraction symbol represents the number of
66 missing species in the database of a classifier for a certain DMC. Solving each equation represent the number of FNs of a
67 classifier for a DMC should all missing species be present in the database and correctly classified by the classifier. The last
68 column shows the total of all DMCs per classifier. Bracken and CCMetagen are omitted, they have the same values as
69 Kraken2 and KMA, respectively.

70

71 4. Detection of *Bacillus* production strains and contaminants in food 72 enzyme products

73 4.1. Text

74 4.1.1. Selection of metric with the best discriminatory power

75 The frequent detection of FPs is a well-recognized issue in the classification of metagenomic samples.
76 Therefore, after classification, a threshold is often used whether or not to consider a detected species
77 present. An effective threshold should filter out all FPs while preserving the TPs. Various metrics can
78 be used to set this threshold, including breadth of coverage, depth, number of aligned reads, and
79 possibly a combination of these factors.

80 After classification, a species was considered present when at least one of its genomes exceeds
81 the chosen metric threshold as there can be multiple detected genomes carrying the same species
82 label. Therefore, to determine the presence of a species, only the genome with the highest chosen
83 metric is relevant. Three metrics were evaluated: template identity, number of aligned bases and the
84 average depth. For every metric, genomes with the highest value were selected per mix and species.
85 A good metric should reach both a precision and recall of 1, indicating a clear separation between FPs
86 from TPs. A precision score less than 1 suggests that some FPs have exceeded the threshold, while a
87 recall score less than 1 indicates that some TPs have fallen below the threshold, resulting in FNs. Figure
88 S4.4 shows a precision-recall curve of the three metrics for such genomes in the 204 *in silico* mixes.
89 The metric template identity was the only metric reaching 1 for both precision and recall. All FPs were
90 filtered out at a threshold of 15.62% with the lowest template identity of the TPs being 33.53%,
91 resulting in a safe range of 17.91%. For the number of aligned bases, precision reached 1 only after a
92 threshold of 12,622,370 bases, which yielded a recall of 0.89 (introducing 44 FNs). Similarly, for depth,
93 precision reached 1 at a threshold of 3.14, resulting in a recall of 0.87 (introducing 52 FNs).

94

95 4.2. Figures

96 Figure S4.1

97

98 Figure S4.1: DNA fragmentation of the five *Bacillus* isolates using the TapeStation 4200. The legend depicts the DNA
99 Integrity Number (DIN) between brackets, ranging from DIN ~1 (very degraded DNA) to DIN 10 (highly intact DNA).Figure

100 S4.2

101

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Figure S4.2: Reads length distribution of the five *Bacillus* isolates. Each plot represent a histogram for one of the five

103

Bacillus isolates. The x-axis is represents the length of the reads (base pairs) with a bin width of 100 (capped at 100,000).

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The y-axis shows the relative frequency (count / total count reads) on a logarithmic scale (capped at 0.2). The read

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distribution of the Bacilli differ slightly. However, for the *in silico* mixes, all five bacilli were subsampled based on the same

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length distribution (i.e., from real FE samples). By using bins to subsample instead of exact lengths and by sampling enough

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reads, the effect of different length distribution in the donor genomes should be minimal. Potential different read length

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distribution of chromosomes and plasmids were not taken into consideration when subsampling. However, if such

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differences introduced a (large) bias, one would expect it to be reflected in the results either through an unusually high

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template ID (if plasmids were underrepresented) or an unusually low template ID (if plasmids were overrepresented), as

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plasmid hits are removed as part of the workflow. Based on Figure 4.3, this was most likely not the case.

113 Figure S4.3

114

115 Figure S4.3: Empirical cumulative distribution of read quality and length for both isolate and *in vitro* mixes sequenced in
116 this study, and 'real' metagenomic datasets of FE. The left plot shows the average read quality on the x-axis, while the right
117 plot displays read length (capped at 50,000bps) on the x-axis. In both the left and right plots, the y-axis represents the
118 percentage of bases with an average read quality or read length less than or equal to the corresponding value on the x-axis,
119 respectively.

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122 Figure S4.4: Diagram of the length transformation process for the *in silico* mixes.

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124 Figure S4.5

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Figure S4.5: Visual presentation of the composition of the 204 *in silico* mixes. The top row displays the five isolates used in the mixes, while the second row illustrates the three types of mixes. The colors indicate which isolate corresponds to each abundance (green for *B. subtilis s.l.* production organisms and yellow for *B. cereus s.l.* contaminants). Type one consists of two 'green isolates' in each mix, each at 50%. Type two includes two 'green isolates' at 45% each, with the yellow isolate contributing 10%. Type three features two isolates from all five isolates, with one isolate ranging from 90% to 99% and another making up the remaining abundance to reach 100%. A full overview of all permutations is also available in Supplementary Table S4.2.

135 Figure S4.6

136

137 Figure S4.6: Precision-recall plots of the 204 *in silico* mixes. Each panel illustrates how precision and recall change as the
138 thresholds for template identity, number of aligned bases and average depth are increased. When a FP is eliminated by a
139 threshold, precision improves, whereas the introduction of a FN causes recall to decrease. A precision and recall of 1
140 indicates the existence of a threshold at which TPs and FPs are perfectly distinguishable.

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142 Figure S4.7

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144 Figure S4.7: Hierarchical clustering of 2087 *B. subtilis* s.l. genomes. All genomes were clustered based on their pairwise ANI
145 values. Values below 98% were masked and the resulting clusters demarcated with a green box. For every green box, a
146 species majority vote was performed and genomes with species not aligning with the majority vote were removed.

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150 Figure S4.8: Length distributions of all applicability FE samples and *in silico* mix 1. The plot depicts a cumulative histogram
 151 with on the x-axis the read length and on the y-axis the relative percentage of reads smaller than the read length on the x-
 152 axis. The length distribution of *in silico* mix 1 is added to compare with the distributions of the real FE samples.

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Figure S4.9: Template identity for the five *in vitro* mixes with either full yield, or downsampled without length transformation. Each panel represent an *in vitro* mix (Table 2) with blue representing the *in vitro* mixes with full yield and orange representing the mixes downsampled to 3M reads without length transformation. The x-axis represent the top 10 highest scoring species marked green for TPs and red for FPs. The y-axis depicts the template identity (%). The red and green dotted lines represent the highest FP and lowest TP template identities, respectively, across the 204 *in silico* mixes (Figure 3). The figure demonstrates that FPs tend to have higher template identities in samples with higher yield because TPs quickly reach their maximum template identity, while FPs have more room for improvement, allowing their template identities to increase further.

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 166 Figure S4.10: Average alignments scores and number of reads that map to *B. paralicheniformis*. The scatter plot displays for
 167 each sample the number of reads aligned to *B. paralicheniformis* on the x-axis and the average alignment score of those
 168 reads on the y-axis. Each dot represents a sample: green dots indicate *in silico* mixes, while blue and orange dots represent
 169 the real FE samples A3 and A4, respectively.

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 171

172 4.3. Tables

173 Table S4.1

	ENA accession	Number of reads	Number of bases	Average length	Median length	N50	Average Phred score	Length transformation	Applicability
A2	ERR9904667	5,143,670	2,791,974,285	542.8	409	670	10.14	Yes	Yes
A3	ERR9904638	5,429,075	3,955,456,047	728.6	556	902	10.48	Yes	Yes
M1	ERR14098131s	2,633,262	2,258,905,504	857.8	528	1,255	9.68	No	Yes
A12	ERR14098658	13,347,460	14,796,200,845	1,108.5	696	1,713	11.23	Yes	Yes
P1	ERR9907954	13,676,337	8,050,723,605	588.7	463	677	12.03	Yes	Yes
A4	ERR9907858	2,355,810	1,856,931,199	788.2	609	968	11.18	Yes	Yes

174 Table S4.1: Accession and read metrics of six commercial FE products. The first and second column denotes the sample name and ENA accession. The third, fourth, fifth, sixth, seventh and
 175 eighth column show the number of reads, the number of bases, the average read length, the median read length, the N50 and the average Phred score, respectively. The ninth and tenth
 176 column displays if the sample was used for the length transformation model and/or for the applicability analysis.

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	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	<i>B. licheniformis</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. velezensis</i>	<i>B. paranthracis</i>
mix 1	50	50	0	0	0
mix 2	50	0	50	0	0
mix 3	50	0	0	50	0
mix 4	0	50	50	0	0
mix 5	0	50	0	50	0
mix 6	0	0	50	50	0
mix 7	90	10	0	0	0
mix 8	90	0	10	0	0
mix 9	90	0	0	10	0
mix 10	0	90	10	0	0
mix 11	0	90	0	10	0
mix 12	10	90	0	0	0
mix 13	0	0	90	10	0
mix 14	10	0	90	0	0
mix 15	0	10	90	0	0
mix 16	10	0	0	90	0
mix 17	0	10	0	90	0
mix 18	0	0	10	90	0
mix 19	45	45	0	0	10
mix 20	45	0	45	0	10
mix 21	45	0	0	45	10
mix 22	0	45	45	0	10
mix 23	0	45	0	45	10
mix 24	0	0	45	45	10
mix 25	1	99	0	0	0
mix 26	1	0	99	0	0
mix 27	1	0	0	99	0
mix 28	1	0	0	0	99
mix 29	99	1	0	0	0
mix 30	0	1	99	0	0
mix 31	0	1	0	99	0
mix 32	0	1	0	0	99
mix 33	99	0	1	0	0
mix 34	0	99	1	0	0
mix 35	0	0	1	99	0
mix 36	0	0	1	0	99
mix 37	99	0	0	1	0
mix 38	0	99	0	1	0
mix 39	0	0	99	1	0
mix 40	0	0	0	1	99
mix 41	99	0	0	0	1

mix 42	0	99	0	0	1
mix 43	0	0	99	0	1
mix 44	0	0	0	99	1
mix 45	2	98	0	0	0
mix 46	2	0	98	0	0
mix 47	2	0	0	98	0
mix 48	2	0	0	0	98
mix 49	98	2	0	0	0
mix 50	0	2	98	0	0
mix 51	0	2	0	98	0
mix 52	0	2	0	0	98
mix 53	98	0	2	0	0
mix 54	0	98	2	0	0
mix 55	0	0	2	98	0
mix 56	0	0	2	0	98
mix 57	98	0	0	2	0
mix 58	0	98	0	2	0
mix 59	0	0	98	2	0
mix 60	0	0	0	2	98
mix 61	98	0	0	0	2
mix 62	0	98	0	0	2
mix 63	0	0	98	0	2
mix 64	0	0	0	98	2
mix 65	3	97	0	0	0
mix 66	3	0	97	0	0
mix 67	3	0	0	97	0
mix 68	3	0	0	0	97
mix 69	97	3	0	0	0
mix 70	0	3	97	0	0
mix 71	0	3	0	97	0
mix 72	0	3	0	0	97
mix 73	97	0	3	0	0
mix 74	0	97	3	0	0
mix 75	0	0	3	97	0
mix 76	0	0	3	0	97
mix 77	97	0	0	3	0
mix 78	0	97	0	3	0
mix 79	0	0	97	3	0
mix 80	0	0	0	3	97
mix 81	97	0	0	0	3
mix 82	0	97	0	0	3
mix 83	0	0	97	0	3
mix 84	0	0	0	97	3
mix 85	4	96	0	0	0
mix 86	4	0	96	0	0

mix 87	4	0	0	96	0
mix 88	4	0	0	0	96
mix 89	96	4	0	0	0
mix 90	0	4	96	0	0
mix 91	0	4	0	96	0
mix 92	0	4	0	0	96
mix 93	96	0	4	0	0
mix 94	0	96	4	0	0
mix 95	0	0	4	96	0
mix 96	0	0	4	0	96
mix 97	96	0	0	4	0
mix 98	0	96	0	4	0
mix 99	0	0	96	4	0
mix 100	0	0	0	4	96
mix 101	96	0	0	0	4
mix 102	0	96	0	0	4
mix 103	0	0	96	0	4
mix 104	0	0	0	96	4
mix 105	5	95	0	0	0
mix 106	5	0	95	0	0
mix 107	5	0	0	95	0
mix 108	5	0	0	0	95
mix 109	95	5	0	0	0
mix 110	0	5	95	0	0
mix 111	0	5	0	95	0
mix 112	0	5	0	0	95
mix 113	95	0	5	0	0
mix 114	0	95	5	0	0
mix 115	0	0	5	95	0
mix 116	0	0	5	0	95
mix 117	95	0	0	5	0
mix 118	0	95	0	5	0
mix 119	0	0	95	5	0
mix 120	0	0	0	5	95
mix 121	95	0	0	0	5
mix 122	0	95	0	0	5
mix 123	0	0	95	0	5
mix 124	0	0	0	95	5
mix 125	6	94	0	0	0
mix 126	6	0	94	0	0
mix 127	6	0	0	94	0
mix 128	6	0	0	0	94
mix 129	94	6	0	0	0
mix 130	0	6	94	0	0
mix 131	0	6	0	94	0

mix 132	0	6	0	0	94
mix 133	94	0	6	0	0
mix 134	0	94	6	0	0
mix 135	0	0	6	94	0
mix 136	0	0	6	0	94
mix 137	94	0	0	6	0
mix 138	0	94	0	6	0
mix 139	0	0	94	6	0
mix 140	0	0	0	6	94
mix 141	94	0	0	0	6
mix 142	0	94	0	0	6
mix 143	0	0	94	0	6
mix 144	0	0	0	94	6
mix 145	7	93	0	0	0
mix 146	7	0	93	0	0
mix 147	7	0	0	93	0
mix 148	7	0	0	0	93
mix 149	93	7	0	0	0
mix 150	0	7	93	0	0
mix 151	0	7	0	93	0
mix 152	0	7	0	0	93
mix 153	93	0	7	0	0
mix 154	0	93	7	0	0
mix 155	0	0	7	93	0
mix 156	0	0	7	0	93
mix 157	93	0	0	7	0
mix 158	0	93	0	7	0
mix 159	0	0	93	7	0
mix 160	0	0	0	7	93
mix 161	93	0	0	0	7
mix 162	0	93	0	0	7
mix 163	0	0	93	0	7
mix 164	0	0	0	93	7
mix 165	8	92	0	0	0
mix 166	8	0	92	0	0
mix 167	8	0	0	92	0
mix 168	8	0	0	0	92
mix 169	92	8	0	0	0
mix 170	0	8	92	0	0
mix 171	0	8	0	92	0
mix 172	0	8	0	0	92
mix 173	92	0	8	0	0
mix 174	0	92	8	0	0
mix 175	0	0	8	92	0
mix 176	0	0	8	0	92

mix 177	92	0	0	8	0
mix 178	0	92	0	8	0
mix 179	0	0	92	8	0
mix 180	0	0	0	8	92
mix 181	92	0	0	0	8
mix 182	0	92	0	0	8
mix 183	0	0	92	0	8
mix 184	0	0	0	92	8
mix 185	9	91	0	0	0
mix 186	9	0	91	0	0
mix 187	9	0	0	91	0
mix 188	9	0	0	0	91
mix 189	91	9	0	0	0
mix 190	0	9	91	0	0
mix 191	0	9	0	91	0
mix 192	0	9	0	0	91
mix 193	91	0	9	0	0
mix 194	0	91	9	0	0
mix 195	0	0	9	91	0
mix 196	0	0	9	0	91
mix 197	91	0	0	9	0
mix 198	0	91	0	9	0
mix 199	0	0	91	9	0
mix 200	0	0	0	9	91
mix 201	91	0	0	0	9
mix 202	0	91	0	0	9
mix 203	0	0	91	0	9
mix 204	0	0	0	91	9

180 Table S4.2: Relative abundances of the five species in each of the 204 *in silico* mixes. The first column shows the mix
181 number. The other columns represent the relative percentage of the five Bacilli present in the mix.

182

Species	Genome count
<i>Bacillus anthracis</i>	1,588
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	1,334
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	751
<i>Bacillus paranthracis</i>	514
<i>Bacillus toyonensis</i>	372
<i>Bacillus wiedmannii</i>	362
<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	253
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	247
<i>Bacillus weihenstephanensis</i>	191
<i>Bacillus tropicus</i>	147
<i>Bacillus mycoides</i>	140
<i>Bacillus pseudomycooides</i>	128
<i>Bacillus nitratireducens</i>	96
<i>Bacillus pacificus</i>	87
<i>Bacillus mobilis</i>	85
<i>Bacillus luti</i>	43
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	37
<i>Bacillus altitudinis</i>	31
<i>Bacillus albus</i>	28
<i>Bacillus cytotoxicus</i>	26
<i>Bacillus paralicheniformis</i>	18
<i>Bacillus safensis</i>	17
<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	17
<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>	16
<i>Bacillus paramobilis</i>	14
<i>Bacillus paramycooides</i>	13
<i>Bacillus bingmayongensis</i>	12
<i>Bacillus halotolerans</i>	10
<i>Bacillus proteolyticus</i>	9
<i>Bacillus hominis</i>	7
<i>Bacillus atrophaeus</i>	6

<i>Bacillus spizizenii</i>	6
<i>Bacillus glycinifermentans</i>	4
<i>Bacillus siamensis</i>	4
<i>Bacillus inaquosorum</i>	3
<i>Bacillus vallismortis</i>	3
<i>Bacillus methanolicus</i>	2
<i>Bacillus rhizoplanae</i>	2
<i>Bacillus clarus</i>	2
<i>Bacillus fungorum</i>	2
<i>Bacillus mojavenensis</i>	2
<i>Bacillus gaemokensis</i>	2
<i>Bacillus manliponensis</i>	1
<i>Bacillus aquiflavi</i>	1
<i>Bacillus fonticola</i>	1
<i>Bacillus rugosus</i>	1
<i>Bacillus infantis</i>	1
<i>Bacillus shivajii</i>	1
<i>Bacillus haynesii</i>	1
<i>Bacillus weihaiensis</i>	1
<i>Bacillus xiamenensis</i>	1
<i>Bacillus zhangzhouensis</i>	1
<i>Bacillus aerophilus</i>	1
<i>Bacillus sonorensis</i>	1
<i>Bacillus tequilensis</i>	1
<i>Bacillus smithii</i>	1
<i>Bacillus badius</i>	1
<i>Bacillus cabrialesii</i>	1
<i>Bacillus arachidis</i>	1

184 Table S4.3: Number of genomes per species of the *Bacillus* genus.

185

186 Table S4.4

	Species	Relative abundance (%)	DNA (ng)
Mix 1	<i>B. licheniformis</i>	75	750
	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	22,5	225
	<i>B. velezensis</i>	2,5	25
Mix 2	<i>B. velezensis</i>	80	800
	<i>B. licheniformis</i>	20	200
Mix 3	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	76,5	765
	<i>B. licheniformis</i>	22,5	225
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	1	10
Mix 4	<i>B. licheniformis</i>	75	750
	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	20	200
	<i>B. cereus</i>	5	50
Mix 5	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	20	200
	<i>B. licheniformis</i>	20	200
	<i>B. velezensis</i>	20	200
	<i>B. subtilis</i>	20	200
	<i>B. cereus</i>	20	200

187 Table S4.4: DNA amount mix per species per group. For each mix a total of 1000 ng of DNA mix was prepared following the
188 abundance designated in the third column.

189 Table S4.5

	Number of bases in mix	Number of bases with read length higher than 15k	Bases with multiple mapping references	Bases with at least one MAPQ < 60	Bases with overlapping sections	Bases with coverage < 80%	Bases after filter steps	Ratio bases of filtered to unfiltered mix
Mix 1	32,668,427,519	12,389,389,335	1,151,406,506	559,309,732	1,551,036,252	358,560,570	16,658,725,124	51%
Mix 2	30,979,842,193	7,119,653,459	834,540,320	580,836,661	1,086,969,389	659,642,947	20,698,199,417	67%
Mix 3	24,974,818,719	12,545,616,083	1,083,925,006	174,050,733	760,660,575	106,373,266	10,304,193,056	41%
Mix 4	24,644,907,350	8,629,675,614	1,384,688,276	313,006,939	957,431,471	220,233,389	13,139,871,661	53%
Mix 5	28,588,330,396	17,675,329,649	1,471,154,202	209,831,323	557,174,623	160,632,874	8,514,207,725	30%

190 Table S4.5: Number of bases at each filter step in the high confidence selection process of the five *in vitro* mixes. The first column denotes the name of the mix with the number of raw bases
 191 in the second column. The third through seventh columns indicate the number of bases removed at each step of the process, in order. The eighth column and ninth column show the final
 192 number of bases and fraction of bases with respect to the raw number of bases, respectively, after the all process steps.

193

194 Table S4.6

	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i>	<i>B. licheniformis</i>	<i>B. paranthracis</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>B. velezensis</i>
Mix 1	42,496 1,284,347,268	489,167 14,234,381,349	NA	NA	38,176 1,086,213,216
Mix 2	NA	129,405 3,629,086,002	NA	NA	602,792 17,040,565,206
Mix 3	184,599 5,904,826,215	140,626 4,103,037,508	NA	9,197 270,625,273	NA
Mix 4	179,838 5,966,857,759	231,394 6,528,335,867	24,531 603,534,281	NA	NA
Mix 5	34,476 1,065,289,372	71,910 2,032,926,366	48,317 1,162,371,885	96,527 3,045,131,698	43,945 1,154,434,377

195 Table S4.6: Number of reads and bases per species retained after the high confidence selection process.

Mix	Type	Reference	numreads	covbases	coverage	mean depth	mean baseq	mean mapq
Mix 1	Unfiltered	NZ_CP018902.1	94,240	4,002,836	100.00	375.1	31.3	54.8
		NZ_CP038186.1	763,913	4,152,720	98.16	3901.0	31.1	57.9
		NZ_CP076119.1	55,629	3,943,400	96.52	303.9	31.4	58.3
	Filtered	NZ_CP018902.1	44,485	4,002,836	100.00	317.5	31.5	60.0
		NZ_CP038186.1	532,973	4,151,754	98.14	3281.2	31.5	60.0
		NZ_CP076119.1	41,051	3,923,977	96.05	257.9	31.7	60.0
Mix 2	Unfiltered	NZ_CP038186.1	220,689	4,147,047	98.03	988.7	32.0	56.3
		NZ_CP076119.1	832,923	3,965,308	97.06	4494.1	32.2	58.9
	Filtered	NZ_CP038186.1	137,881	4,142,812	97.93	836.3	32.4	60.0
		NZ_CP076119.1	661,693	3,957,741	96.88	4045.0	32.4	60.0
Mix 3	Unfiltered	NZ_CP018902.1	329,434	4,002,836	100.00	1668.9	31.2	59.0
		NZ_CP038186.1	234,287	4,148,836	98.07	1186.3	31.3	57.9
		NZ_OX419579.1	20,155	4,232,781	99.26	76.9	31.1	58.8
	Filtered	NZ_CP018902.1	201,679	4,002,836	100.00	1459.9	31.8	60.0
		NZ_CP038186.1	150,613	4,146,144	98.01	945.9	31.9	60.0
		NZ_OX419579.1	9,531	4,226,741	99.11	62.9	32.0	60.0
Mix 4	Unfiltered	NZ_CP018902.1	269,335	4,002,836	100.00	1690.7	30.5	58.9
		NZ_CP048687.1	52,844	5,358,047	94.20	128.4	31.7	57.0
		NZ_CP038186.1	409,719	4,149,968	98.10	1858.6	30.3	57.8
	Filtered	NZ_CP018902.1	188,019	4,002,836	100.00	1473.4	31.2	60.0
		NZ_CP048687.1	25,554	5,299,158	93.17	104.4	32.7	60.0
		NZ_CP038186.1	251,624	4,146,847	98.02	1503.5	31.2	60.0
Mix 5	Unfiltered	NZ_CP018902.1	74,447	4,002,836	100.00	329.3	30.6	57.8
		NZ_CP038186.1	130,044	4,146,272	98.01	611.0	30.6	57.6
		NZ_OX419579.1	223,679	4,230,966	99.21	848.5	30.2	58.9
		NZ_CP048687.1	125,130	5,380,697	94.60	258.2	31.7	56.8
		NZ_CP076119.1	71,508	3,945,763	96.58	348.9	30.8	58.7
	Filtered	NZ_CP018902.1	35,921	4,002,836	100.00	263.2	31.3	60.0
		NZ_CP038186.1	77,092	4,143,017	97.93	468.4	31.3	60.0
		NZ_OX419579.1	104,655	4,227,949	99.14	706.9	31.0	60.0
		NZ_CP048687.1	50,851	5,310,130	93.36	201.0	32.6	60.0
		NZ_CP076119.1	47,152	3,925,513	96.09	274.1	31.4	60.0

197 Table S4.7: The mapping metrics of the five *in vitro* mixes, both unfiltered and filtered. The first column denotes the *in vitro*
 198 mix, while the second column shows whether the sample is unfiltered or filtered. Unfiltered represents the raw sample
 199 without any processing and filtered represent the selected 'high confidence' reads used for the length transformation of
 200 the *in vitro* mixes. The remaining columns display the mapping metrics of minimap2 with the third, fourth, fifth, sixth,
 201 seventh, eighth and ninth column being the mapped reference, mapped number of reads, number of covered reference
 202 bases, breadth of coverage (%), mean depth, mean base quality of the mapped reads and the mapping quality,
 203 respectively.

Sample name	Species name	Template identity (%)
M1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	26.07
M1	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	98.32
M1	<i>Trichoderma reesei</i>	76.95
M1	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	98.91
A2	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	21.47
A2	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	99.87
A2	<i>Bacillus paralicheniformis</i>	11.09
A3	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	99.97
A3	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	97.83
A3	<i>Bacillus paralicheniformis</i>	18.75
A3	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	33.33
A12	<i>Bacillus cytotoxicus</i>	54.51
A12	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	68.34
A12	<i>Escherichia fergusonii</i>	22.05
A12	<i>Enterococcus casseliflavus</i>	35.09
A12	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	77.13
A12	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	79.18
A12	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	91.16
A12	<i>Lactococcus garvieae</i>	94.25
A12	<i>Sinheimvirus phiX174</i>	15.91
A12	<i>Krischvirus RB49</i>	93.01
A12	<i>Felixounavirus felixO1</i>	21.67
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus YpPY</i>	39.45
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus T7</i>	72.34
A12	<i>Tequintavirus T5</i>	34.58
A12	<i>Vectrevirus K15</i>	10.61
A12	<i>Carltongylesvirus GJ1</i>	49.64
A12	<i>Krischvirus georgiaone</i>	88.88
A12	<i>Macdonaldcampvirus Ville1</i>	11.31
A12	<i>Teetrevirus SGJL2</i>	41.72
A12	<i>Vequintavirus V5</i>	18.48
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus 13a</i>	57.37
A12	<i>Dhillonvirus SSL2009a</i>	41.01
A12	<i>Krischvirus jse</i>	76.06
A12	<i>Drulisvirus KP34</i>	26.29
A12	<i>Felixounavirus wV8</i>	19.08
A12	<i>Dhillonvirus SO1</i>	20.20
A12	<i>Tequintavirus SPC35</i>	62.10
A12	<i>Tequintavirus AKFV33</i>	72.00
A12	<i>Dhillonvirus EP23</i>	55.86
A12	<i>Saphexavirus BC611</i>	70.26

A12	<i>Kuravirus NJ01</i>	34.12
A12	<i>Gamaleyavirus ECBP1</i>	56.45
A12	<i>Dhillonvirus JL1</i>	47.24
A12	<i>Gamaleyavirus IME11</i>	46.72
A12	<i>Vequintavirus FV3</i>	93.29
A12	<i>Dhillonvirus HK578</i>	32.27
A12	<i>Jedunavirus JD001</i>	50.27
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus pSf1</i>	94.70
A12	<i>Roufvirus pIS4A</i>	11.71
A12	<i>Saphexavirus SPQS1</i>	42.82
A12	<i>Berlinvirus FE44</i>	20.76
A12	<i>Vequintavirus JES2013</i>	24.41
A12	<i>Kayfunavirus CR44b</i>	17.78
A12	<i>Gamaleyavirus Sb1</i>	62.84
A12	<i>Efquatrovirus EF4</i>	14.81
A12	<i>Drulisvirus F19</i>	17.29
A12	<i>Efquatrovirus EF3</i>	20.75
A12	<i>Vequintavirus FFH2</i>	22.53
A12	<i>Tequintavirus FFH1</i>	49.86
A12	<i>Gamaleyavirus Bp4</i>	50.40
A12	<i>Kayfunavirus PE31</i>	79.68
A12	<i>Jilinvirus ep3</i>	31.07
A12	<i>Krischvirus gec3s</i>	93.37
A12	<i>Dhillonvirus YD2008s</i>	44.70
A12	<i>Felixounavirus UAB87</i>	56.15
A12	<i>Felixounavirus SP116</i>	95.01
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus CICC80001</i>	69.39
A12	<i>Felixounavirus EC6</i>	79.74
A12	<i>Felixounavirus VpaE1</i>	40.58
A12	<i>Seoulvirus SPN3US</i>	96.75
A12	<i>Kagunavirus K1H</i>	44.70
A12	<i>Kagunavirus K1G</i>	60.59
A12	<i>Jilinvirus CVM10</i>	11.58
A12	<i>Vequintavirus slur16</i>	30.73
A12	<i>Drulisvirus Kp2</i>	27.60
A12	<i>Drulisvirus KpV41</i>	19.51
A12	<i>Tequintavirus shivani</i>	12.21
A12	<i>Drulisvirus SU552A</i>	11.35
A12	<i>Webervirus sushi</i>	15.36
A12	<i>Drulisvirus SU503</i>	10.45
A12	<i>Felixounavirus AYO145A</i>	69.01
A12	<i>Efquatrovirus IME196</i>	51.66
A12	<i>Webervirus wv1513</i>	19.62
A12	<i>Berlinvirus P483</i>	54.11
A12	<i>Schiekvirus EFDG1</i>	77.76

A12	<i>Felixounavirus HY02</i>	53.50
A12	<i>Felixounavirus JH2</i>	92.27
A12	<i>Berlinvirus P694</i>	21.89
A12	<i>Tequintavirus slur09</i>	84.26
A12	<i>Kuravirus kv1721</i>	46.08
A12	<i>Teetrevirus CFP1</i>	34.41
A12	<i>Webervirus KP36</i>	12.09
A12	<i>Teetrevirus SH2</i>	50.53
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus tv64795ec1</i>	61.60
A12	<i>Webervirus PKP126</i>	22.47
A12	<i>Tequintavirus SHSML45</i>	10.87
A12	<i>Felixounavirus Alf5</i>	31.55
A12	<i>Kayfunavirus SH3</i>	43.82
A12	<i>Tequintavirus NR01</i>	86.13
A12	<i>Drulisvirus KpV475</i>	15.20
A12	<i>Efquatrovirus EcZ22</i>	26.67
A12	<i>Saltrevirus sv64795sal3</i>	39.26
A12	<i>Felixounavirus BPS15Q2</i>	71.52
A12	<i>Shuimuvirus IME207</i>	44.27
A12	<i>Comamonas kerstersii</i>	11.33
A12	<i>Salvovirus salvo</i>	11.62
A12	<i>Saphexavirus VD13</i>	45.58
A12	<i>Tequintavirus APCEc03</i>	53.68
A12	<i>Vequintavirus APECc02</i>	21.35
A12	<i>Teetrevirus YeF10</i>	34.23
A12	<i>Vequintavirus murica</i>	28.97
A12	<i>Teetrevirus SM93Y</i>	21.93
A12	<i>Kayfunavirus ZG49</i>	34.21
A12	<i>Mydovirus BIS47</i>	14.31
A12	<i>Kagunavirus K1ind1</i>	39.61
A12	<i>Kagunavirus K1ind2</i>	49.83
A12	<i>Jedunavirus KpV80</i>	66.01
A12	<i>Sashavirus sasha</i>	72.85
A12	<i>Drulisvirus KPV811</i>	62.74
A12	<i>Gamaleyavirus EC1UPM</i>	45.94
A12	<i>Schiekvirus EFP01</i>	92.94
A12	<i>Kayfunavirus F</i>	26.29
A12	<i>Felixounavirus Si3</i>	18.26
A12	<i>Felixounavirus mushroom</i>	23.10
A12	<i>Tequintavirus LLS</i>	60.91
A12	<i>Jilinvirus ECOO78</i>	18.86
A12	<i>Skatevirus LPST10</i>	15.32
A12	<i>Krischvirus ecd7</i>	86.06
A12	<i>Vequintavirus V18</i>	36.66
A12	<i>Saphexavirus IMEEF1</i>	76.45

A12	<i>Saphexavirus SAP6</i>	63.74
A12	<i>Kayfunavirus ST31</i>	63.73
A12	<i>Felixounavirus TP1</i>	25.58
A12	<i>Carltongylesvirus ST32</i>	12.38
A12	<i>Tequintavirus OSYSP</i>	37.65
A12	<i>Yonseivirus N137</i>	17.72
A12	<i>Webervirus N141</i>	24.09
A12	<i>Teetrevirus tv10164302</i>	44.70
A12	<i>Teetrevirus 2050H2</i>	31.47
A12	<i>Cedarrivervirus Sf11</i>	34.52
A12	<i>Efquatrovirus SHEF2</i>	10.89
A12	<i>Efquatrovirus SHEF4</i>	19.31
A12	<i>Nonagvirus SE1Kor</i>	32.45
A12	<i>Drulisvirus KpS2</i>	17.47
A12	<i>Tequintavirus SP01</i>	94.54
A12	<i>Jedunavirus KpV52</i>	42.39
A12	<i>Justusliebigvirus PHB05</i>	70.04
A12	<i>Tequintavirus SSP1</i>	89.63
A12	<i>Tequintavirus chee24</i>	12.28
A12	<i>Kagunavirus golestan</i>	57.78
A12	<i>Peatvirus peat2</i>	47.16
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus EG1</i>	94.21
A12	<i>Felixounavirus BPS17L1</i>	63.62
A12	<i>Felixounavirus BPS17W1</i>	79.56
A12	<i>Webervirus KpCol1</i>	18.43
A12	<i>Vectrevirus CrRp3</i>	62.14
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus HZ2R8</i>	76.18
A12	<i>Kayfunavirus YZ1</i>	31.08
A12	<i>Drulisvirus SFN6B</i>	81.77
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus YpsPG</i>	32.00
A12	<i>Buchananvirus Sa179lw</i>	19.47
A12	<i>Plesiomonas shigelloides</i>	13.37
A12	<i>Efquatrovirus AL3</i>	10.63
A12	<i>Tequintavirus gostya9</i>	16.37
A12	<i>Berlinvirus S523</i>	12.92
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus tv3A8767</i>	72.05
A12	<i>Tequintavirus S131</i>	55.95
A12	<i>Skatevirus skate</i>	24.04
A12	<i>Krischvirus kfsec</i>	73.10
A12	<i>Kayfunavirus Vec13</i>	11.99
A12	<i>Webervirus NJS1</i>	32.46
A12	<i>Webervirus TAH8</i>	42.63
A12	<i>Klebsiella virus NJS2</i>	35.37
A12	<i>Skatevirus VSt472</i>	38.66
A12	<i>Justusliebigvirus PD06</i>	55.52

A12	<i>Novemvirus T5282H</i>	29.99
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus N30</i>	95.40
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus C5</i>	79.02
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus IME390</i>	94.98
A12	<i>Schiekvirus EfV12</i>	95.47
A12	<i>Pylasvirus pylas</i>	32.99
A12	<i>Deseoctovirus C1</i>	66.57
A12	<i>Webervirus TSK1</i>	39.22
A12	<i>Wadgaonvirus wv5004651</i>	11.50
A12	<i>Webervirus KpKT21phi1</i>	32.28
A12	<i>Segzyvirus segz1</i>	12.98
A12	<i>Skatevirus Seszw1</i>	40.31
A12	<i>Skatevirus SeSz2</i>	24.10
A12	<i>Minhovirus zip</i>	27.82
A12	<i>Webervirus GHK3</i>	28.75
A12	<i>Teseptimavirus NCA</i>	72.02
A12	<i>Drulivirus minorna</i>	89.43
A12	<i>Tequintavirus SP15</i>	52.90
A12	<i>Akiravirus akira</i>	38.11
A12	<i>Berlinvirus A7</i>	85.49
A12	<i>Kagunavirus RP180</i>	64.11
A12	<i>Webervirus FZ10</i>	13.48
A12	<i>Deseoctovirus DS8</i>	58.64
A12	<i>Tequintavirus HdH2</i>	30.60
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus G292</i>	19.98
A12	<i>Skatevirus KFSSE2</i>	11.21
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus henu8</i>	86.79
A12	<i>Tequintavirus Th1</i>	82.07
A12	<i>Pylasvirus KpCHEMY26</i>	62.89
A12	<i>Tequintavirus VSe12</i>	31.82
A12	<i>Webervirus sin4</i>	21.97
A12	<i>Webervirus sweeny</i>	17.21
A12	<i>Webervirus skenny</i>	12.57
A12	<i>Webervirus shelby</i>	19.61
A12	<i>Carltongylesvirus mangalitsa</i>	46.04
A12	<i>Webervirus domnhall</i>	20.95
A12	<i>Webervirus IMGroot</i>	21.14
A12	<i>Webervirus call</i>	19.12
A12	<i>Tequintavirus SE11</i>	95.82
A12	<i>Yonseivirus soft</i>	18.97
A12	<i>Epseptimavirus ev23</i>	10.57
A12	<i>Tequintavirus VEc33</i>	41.29
A12	<i>Lactococcus petauri</i>	64.26
A12	<i>Webervirus wv13</i>	21.08
A12	<i>Enterococcus gallinarum</i>	16.99

A12	<i>Webervirus KLPPOU149</i>	10.61
A12	<i>Skatevirus BS5</i>	21.76
A12	<i>Webervirus KpNIH2</i>	20.43
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus aaroes</i>	22.30
A12	<i>Justusliebigvirus alia</i>	18.67
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus damhaus</i>	14.50
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus egaa</i>	58.39
A12	<i>Carltongylesvirus flopper</i>	31.63
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus grams</i>	38.13
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus haarsle</i>	11.85
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus herni</i>	20.21
A12	<i>Justusliebigvirus muut</i>	13.09
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus vojen</i>	64.46
A12	<i>Tequintavirus L6jm</i>	87.55
A12	<i>Tequintavirus NBEco001</i>	42.11
A12	<i>Tequintavirus NBEco002</i>	45.66
A12	<i>Tequintavirus NBSal003</i>	42.24
A12	<i>Tequintavirus NBSal005</i>	68.07
A12	<i>Astrithrvirus astrithr</i>	40.96
A12	<i>Tequintavirus oldekolle</i>	37.25
A12	<i>Hanrivervirus slyngel</i>	25.59
A12	<i>Enterococcus lactis</i>	20.32
A12	<i>Caminolopintovirus STGO351</i>	39.75
A12	<i>Swiduvovirus swi2</i>	52.99
A12	<i>Segzyvirus LPSTLL</i>	26.83
A12	<i>Shigella flexneri</i>	13.00
A12	<i>Lactococcus formosensis</i>	66.64
A12	<i>Exiguobacterium marinum</i>	44.45
A12	<i>Enterococcus cecorum</i>	87.06
A12	<i>Tequintavirus mar004NP2</i>	56.15
P1	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	96.10
P1	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	98.63
A4	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	98.16
A4	<i>Bacillus paralicheniformis</i>	16.72
A4	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	40.08
A4	<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i>	99.96

206 Table S4.8: All detected species in the six FE samples with a template identity higher than 10. The first column denotes the
207 sample name. The second and third column shows the found species with its corresponding template identity.

208

209 Table S4.9

	Number of bases/reads	Number of bases/reads after downsampling to 3M reads	Number of bases/reads after downsampling + quality filters	Number of bases/reads after quality filter without downsampling
A2	2,791,974,285 5,143,670	1,626,360,200 3,000,000	379,315,712 252,902	649,668,514 434,299
A3	3,955,456,047 5,429,075	2,184,947,559 3,000,000	840,525,094 527,307	1,520,213,416 953,672
M1	2,258,905,504 2,633,262	2,258,905,504 2,633,262	1,164,818,443 625,741	1,164,818,443 625,741
A12	14,796,200,845 13,347,460	3,326,323,740 3,000,000	2,148,585,147 976,321	9,556,014,624 4,345,003
P1	8,050,723,605 13,676,337	1,765,715,225 3,000,000	480,875,859 323,076	2,185,046,325 1,468,396
A4	1,856,931,199 2,355,810	1,856,931,199 2,355,810	807,228,584 501,637	807,228,584 501,637

210 Table S4.9: Number of bases and reads of the six real FE samples used for assessing applicability. The first column denotes the names of the samples. The second column shows the number of
 211 bases/reads in each sample without any processing. The third and fourth column shows the number of leftover bases/reads after downsampling to 3M reads and an additional quality filter (Q
 212 > 7 and L > 1000) step, respectively. The last column shows the number of bases/reads after the quality filter step without first downsampling.

213

214 Table S4.10

Mix	Species	qPCR Method	Rel. abundance (%)	ng	Cq	Estimated target copy number
1	<i>B. subtilis</i>	BSG	95	9.5	13	10 ¹⁰
	<i>B. cereus</i>	BCG	5	0.5	25.6	10 ⁶
2	<i>B. subtilis</i>	BSG	99	9.9	11,7	10 ⁹
	<i>B. cereus</i>	BSG	1	0.1	28.1	10 ⁵

215 Table S4.10: qPCR results from *Bacillus subtilis* group (BSG) and *Bacillus cereus* group (BCG) methods applied on mixes: (1)
216 95% *B. subtilis* + 5% *B. cereus*; and (2) 99% *B. subtilis* + 1% *B. cereus*. For each PCR reaction, a total of 10 ng of DNA was
217 tested. BSG method was performed as mentioned in Fraiture *et al.* ⁴ and the BCG method was performed as described in
218 <https://food.r-biopharm.com/products/surefood-bac-bacillus-cereus-group-plus/ref>.

219

220 5. Filtering for truth: robust KMA-based bioinformatics workflow for 221 high-precision taxonomic classification in Nanopore shotgun 222 metagenomics

223 5.1. Text

224 5.1.1. DMC composition

225 The same nine DMCs with public nanopore sequencing data available from an earlier study were used
226 ¹, with minor modifications. Specifically, one DMC with ONT R9 chemistry was replaced by an ONT R10
227 dataset. Another DMC had both an R9 and R10 dataset in the earlier study, but both were excluded
228 from this study, and instead replaced with a higher-quality R10 dataset for the same DMC.
229 Additionally, an R10 dataset of a new DMC was added. The samples included a mix of: solely bacteria;
230 bacteria with fungi; bacteria with archaea; or all three groups together. Their complexity ranged from
231 simple with only 10 different species to more complex with over 60 species. Species were distributed
232 in three ways: even (all species equally abundant), staggered (different abundances without a
233 constant factor, although equal abundances occurred) or logarithmic (different abundances with each
234 species one-tenth as abundant as the previous one). Hence, the DMCs provide a broad representation
235 of possible metagenomic samples, excluding viruses. PDMC composition

236 The products were purchased either online or from local stores and sequenced in-house.
237 According to their labels, the products contained between one and fourteen species (Supplementary
238 Table S5.8). The labelled species composition was used as the reference truth.

239 5.1.2. DMCs and database taxonomic consistency

240 To ensure taxonomic consistency between the DMCs and the employed reference database, all
241 species names were updated with TaxonKit 0.18.0² to reflect the taxonomy as of February 2023, when
242 the reference database was created. For nearly all organisms in the DMCs, genome assemblies were
243 available on NCBI, where an automatic taxonomy check based on the average nucleotide ID is
244 performed³. In some cases, the submitted name of the assembly did not match the taxonomy of
245 NCBI's check. In such cases, species names in our datasets were corrected to match the taxonomy of
246 NCBI's check. A full overview of updated species names can be found in Supplementary Table S5.2,
247 with further detail in the Supplementary Text.

248 5.1.3. PDMCs and database taxonomic consistency

249 Species names were harmonized according to the NCBI taxonomy (as of February 2023; see Section
250 5.1.2). Updated species names are provided in Supplementary Table S5.8. As no genome assemblies
251 were available for these strains, potential taxonomic misannotations could not be corrected through
252 NCBI's taxonomy check, though some names were manually updated (see Supplementary Text).

253 5.1.4. Abundance conversion

254 The abundance of the three strain madness datasets was in the original study described as taxonomic
255 abundance. To convert this to sequence abundance, the taxonomic abundance of each genome was
256 multiplied with its genome length. The relative sequence abundance was then calculated by dividing
257 each sequence abundance by the total sequence abundance. The abundance of sample HM 276D was
258 expressed in rRNA operon counts; 1,000,000 copies per genome. The rRNA operon abundance was
259 first converted to taxonomic abundance by dividing each species' original abundance by its
260 corresponding average RNA operon copy number, gathered from the *rrnDB*⁴. Afterwards, the
261 sequence abundance of each genome was calculated by multiplying the taxonomic abundance with
262 its genome length. The relative sequence abundance was then calculated by dividing each sequence
263 abundance by the total sequence abundance. Sample HM 277D contained 10,000 to 10,000,000
264 copies per organism. However, because the specific copy numbers per species were not disclosed, this
265 sample was excluded from the LOD analysis. Other samples were originally expressed in sequence
266 abundance, so no conversion was necessary.

267 5.1.5. Update ground truth

268 Due to the changing nature of nomenclature, previously assigned names may no longer be accurate.
269 Since the database was built at a different time than the ground truth labels were defined, taxonomic
270 updates can lead to inaccurate or misleading assignments. These updates generally fall into two types.

271 The first, and simplest, is a straightforward name change, which can be resolved by updating the
272 ground truth label. For example, the ground truth of Zymo D6300 states *Lactobacillus fermentum*, but
273 was changed to *Limosilactobacillus fermentum* in 2020. As such, the labels of each DMC and probiotic-
274 derived mock community were updated to reflect the taxonomy as of February 2023.

275 The second is more complex and involves the splitting of an existing species into two or more
276 distinct species. For example, *Bacillus spizizenii* is a fairly recent species from 2020, which used to be
277 named *Bacillus subtilis*. In such cases, the associated genomes must be re-evaluated to determine
278 whether they belong to the original species or should be reassigned to the newly defined one. For re-
279 evaluation, the automatic taxonomy check of NCBI was used³. Both types of updates are denoted in
280 separate columns of Table S5.8. An exception was the *Pseudomonas fluorescens* genome

281 (GCA_000009225, full name *Pseudomonas [fluorescens] SBW25*) in the strain madness datasets. A
282 BLAST search revealed an almost identical match to a *Pseudomonas marginalis* genome
283 (GCF_034424355, full name *Pseudomonas marginalis SBW25*). This *P. marginalis* passed NCBI's
284 taxonomy check. As a result, *P. fluorescens* was updated to *P. marginalis*.

285 For the probiotic-derived mock communities, re-evaluation of the species was more difficult as
286 species in the probiotic-derived mock communities are often proprietary and their genomes are not
287 readily available. Although an automated check through NCBI's taxonomy check was therefore not
288 possible, a few species names were still manually updated. The strain *Lactobacillus casei* PXN® 37™
289 from sample PROBIOTIC 8 is not listed on NCBI. However, a literature search indicates that this strain
290 is also known as *Lactobacillus casei* NCIMB 30185^{5,6}, which updated to the taxonomy of February 2023
291 should be *Lacticaseibacillus casei* NCIMB 30185. Given that another study proposed reclassifying it as
292 *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei*⁷ and our results strongly support this classification, the name was
293 updated accordingly to *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei*. The sample PROBIOTIC 10 contained
294 *Lacticaseibacillus casei* R0215. Although the strain is not described in literature, other probiotic
295 products describe the strain as *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei* R0215, even other probiotic products from
296 same brand as PROBIOTIC 10. Additionally, a BLAST search of the sample to both species shows the
297 majority of the reads mapping to *L. paracasei* (results not shown). Based on this information, along
298 with our own classification results, *Lacticaseibacillus casei* in PROBIOTIC 10 was reclassified as
299 *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei*.

300 5.1.6. Validation of the standard versus the novel approach using PDMCs

301 Figure S5.3 compares the standard and novel approaches by showing the median precision, recall, and
302 F1 scores across ten PDMCs under three selection strategies (no thresholds applied, maximum F1
303 score, and FDR5) and five sample yields. Without any filtering applied, precision declined as yield
304 increased, with values of 83.77% and 55.77% for the novel approach, and 45% and 22.5% for the
305 standard approach, at 200M and 2000M, respectively. The median precision of the standard approach
306 was substantially lower than that of the novel approach, largely due to the detection of many
307 plasmids, which, unlike chromosomal DNA, are typically not species-specific. In contrast, for both
308 approaches, the recall of all PDMCs was 100% across all yields, indicating that all species present in
309 the ground truth were detected. Consequently, the median F1 scores decreased as yields increased,
310 with lower scores for the standard compared to the novel approach, with values of 61.90% and 91.15%
311 at 200M, and 36.67% and 71.43% at 2000M, respectively.

312 Using a maximum F1 score selection strategy, the median precision increased for both approaches.
313 Both approaches achieved perfect median precision, recall, and consequently also F1 scores, of 100%
314 across all yields. However, when not considering solely median values, one sample (PROBIOTIC8) did

315 not reach this perfect score of 100% recall when using the standard approach, which was not the case
316 for the novel approach.

317 Lastly, using FDR5 as selection strategy, the observed performance was similarly higher for the
318 PDMCs compared to the DMCs. The standard and novel approaches reached a median precision of
319 96.15% and 100% across all yields, respectively, although two samples displayed notably lower
320 precision values. For both approaches, a median recall of 100% across all yields was reached. This
321 resulted in corresponding median F1 scores of 98% for the standard approach and 100% for the novel
322 approach across all yields.

323 In conclusion, as with the DMCs, the novel approach performed better for all three selection
324 strategies compared to the standard approach.

325

326 5.2. Tables

327 Table S5.1

Name	Source	Catalog	Instrument	Chemistry version	Basecaller version	Composition	Link	Run accession
Zymo D6300	Zymo Research	D6300	GridION	R9	Guppy v2.2.2	8 bacteria; 2 fungi	https://doi.org/10.1093/qigascience/giz043	ERR2906227
Zymo D6310	Zymo Research	D6310	GridION	R9	Guppy v2.2.2	8 bacteria; 2 fungi	https://doi.org/10.1093/qigascience/giz043	ERR2906229
Zymo D6322	Zymo Research	D6322	PromethION	R10.4.1 LSK114	Dorado 0.7.3	7 bacteria 1 fungus	https://github.com/Kirk3qaar/d/MicroBench	ERR14251398
Zymo D6331	Zymo Research	D6331	PromethION	R10.4.1 SQK- NBD114.24	Dorado 0.8.2	1 archaea; 14 bacteria; 2 fungi	https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-022-01415-8	SRR17913200
Zymo D6332	Zymo Research	D6332	PromethION	R10.4.1 SQK- NBD114.24	Dorado 0.8.2	12 bacteria	https://github.com/Kirk3qaar/d/MicroBench	ERR14789832
Bei Resources HM-276D	Bei Resources	HM-276D	GridION	R9.4 SQK-LSK109	NA	20 bacteria	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2020.101223	SRR11700265
Bei Resources HM-277D	Bei Resources	HM-277D	GridION	R9.4 SQK-LSK109	NA	20 bacteria	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2020.101223	SRR11700264
Strain madness 1	Meslier, V., Quinquis, B., Da Silva, K. et al.	/	NA	R9 SQK-LSK109	Guppy 2.3.1	22 archaea; 45 bacteria	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01762-z	ERR9765780
Strain madness 2						22 archaea; 61 bacteria		ERR9765781
Strain madness 3						14 archaea; 46 bacteria		ERR9765782

328 Table S5.1: Sources and information on the ten DMC. The first, second, and third columns respectively present the DMC name, the company or authors responsible for producing the DMC,
329 and its catalogue number (if applicable). The fourth, fifth, and seventh columns indicate the Nanopore instrument used, the pore chemistry version (along with the kit used, if available), and
330 the software used for basecalling, respectively. The eighth and ninth columns present the source of the DMCs and their corresponding ENA accession numbers, respectively.

331 Table S5.2

	NCBI Reference Genome Accession No.	Original species name	Species name on 02/2023	Changed species name	Genomic DNA (%)
Zymo D6300	GCF_028743795	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	NA	<i>Bacillus spizizenii</i>	12
	GCA_028975465	<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	NA	NA	2
	GCF_028743535	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	NA	NA	12
	GCF_028743555	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NA	NA	12
	GCF_030770375	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	<i>Limosilactobacillus fermentum</i>	NA	12
	GCF_028743575	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	NA	NA	12
	GCF_028743595	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NA	NA	12
	GCA_028975445	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	NA	NA	2
	GCF_028743635	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	NA	NA	12
	GCF_028743615	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	NA	NA	12
Zymo D6310	GCF_028743795	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	NA	<i>Bacillus spizizenii</i>	0.89
	GCA_028975465	<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	NA	NA	0.00089
	GCF_028743535	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	NA	NA	0.00089
	GCF_028743555	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NA	NA	0.089
	GCF_030770375	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	<i>Limosilactobacillus fermentum</i>	NA	0.0089
	GCF_028743575	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	NA	NA	89.1
	GCF_028743595	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NA	NA	8.9
	GCA_028975445	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	NA	NA	0.89
	GCF_028743635	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	NA	NA	0.089

	GCF_028743615	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	NA	NA	0.000089
Zymo D6322	GCF_028743795	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	NA	<i>Bacillus spizizenii</i>	14
	GCF_028743535	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	NA	NA	14
	GCF_028743555	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NA	NA	14
	GCF_028743575	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	NA	NA	14
	GCF_028743595	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NA	NA	14
	GCA_028975445	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	NA	NA	2
	GCF_028743635	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	NA	NA	14
	GCF_028743615	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	NA	NA	14
Zymo D6331	GCF_028743255	<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	NA	NA	1.5
	GCF_028743275	<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	NA	NA	14
	GCF_028743295	<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	NA	NA	6
	NA	<i>Candida albicans</i>	NA	NA	1.5
	GCF_028743315	<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	NA	NA	1.5
	GCF_028743735	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	NA	NA	0.0001
	NA	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	NA	NA	0.001
	GCF_028743355	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NA	NA	14
	GCF_028743335				
	GCF_028743755				
	GCF_028743555				
	GCF_028743375				
	GCF_028743395	<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	NA	NA	14
	GCF_028743415	<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	NA	NA	6
GCF_028743095	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	<i>Limosilactobacillus fermentum</i>	NA	6	

	GCF_028743435	<i>Methanobrevibacter smithii</i>	NA	NA	0.1	
	GCF_028743775	<i>Prevotella corporis</i>	NA	NA	6	
	GCF_028743455	<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	NA	NA	14	
	GCA_030867715	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	NA	NA	1.4	
	GCF_028743635	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	NA	NA	0.01	
	GCF_028743475	<i>Veillonella rogosae</i>	NA	NA	14	
Zymo D6332	GCF_031191795	<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	NA	NA	1	
	GCF_031191205	<i>Haemophilus parainfluenzae</i>	NA	NA	8	
	GCF_031190635	<i>Neisseria subflava</i>	NA	NA	16	
	GCF_031323855	<i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i>	NA	NA	1	
	GCF_031191185	<i>Prevotella nigrescens</i>	NA	NA	16	
	GCF_031191775	<i>Rothia dentocariosa</i>	NA	NA	8	
	GCF_031191545	<i>Schaalia odontolytica</i>	NA	NA	8	
	GCF_031191225	<i>Streptococcus mitis</i>	NA	NA	8	
	GCF_044360185	<i>Streptococcus mutans</i>	NA	NA	1	
	GCF_031582885	<i>Streptococcus parasanguinis</i>	NA	NA	16	
	GCF_031192325	<i>Streptococcus salivarius</i>	NA	NA	1	NA
	GCF_031190775	<i>Veillonella parvula</i>	NA	NA	16	NA
HM 276D	GCF_000015425	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	NA	NA	4.86	NA
HM 277D	GCF_000154225	<i>Actinomyces odontolyticus</i>	<i>Schaalia odontolytica</i>	<i>Schaalia dentiphila</i>	5.78	NA
	GCF_000008005	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	NA	<i>Bacillus pacificus</i>	2.87	NA
	GCF_000012825	<i>Bacteroides vulgatus</i>	<i>Phocaeicola vulgatus</i>	NA	5.34	NA
	GCF_000016965	<i>Clostridium beijerinckii</i>	NA	NA	2.86	NA

	GCF_000008565	<i>Deinococcus radiodurans</i>	NA	NA	7.93	NA	
	GCF_000172575	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	NA	NA	4.99	NA	
	GCF_000005845	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NA	NA	4.82	NA	
	GCF_000008525	<i>Helicobacter pylori</i>	NA	NA	6.14	NA	
	GCF_000014425	<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i>	NA	NA	2.7	NA	
	GCF_000196035	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	NA	NA	3.77	NA	
	GCF_000008805	<i>Neisseria meningitidis</i>	NA	NA	4.1	NA	
	GCF_000008345	<i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>	<i>Cutibacterium acnes</i>	NA	6.08	NA	
	GCF_000006765	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NA	NA	11.36	NA	
	GCF_000012905	<i>Rhodobacter sphaeroides</i>	<i>Cereibacter sphaeroides</i>	NA	10.26	NA	
	GCF_000017085	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	NA	NA	3.66	NA	
	GCF_000007645	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	NA	NA	3.3	NA	
	GCF_000007265	<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>	NA	NA	2.25	NA	
	GCF_000007465	<i>Streptococcus mutans</i>	NA	NA	2.94	NA	
	GCF_000006885	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>	NA	NA	4.0	NA	
Strain Madness 1	GCA_000144915	<i>Acidilobus saccharovorans</i>	NA	NA	0.0183	0.018	0.0182
	GCA_000022565	<i>Acidobacterium capsulatum</i>	NA	NA	0.2967	0.2924	0.1825
Strain Madness 2	GCA_000025665	<i>Aciduliprofundum boonei</i>	<i>Candidatus Aciduliprofundum boonei</i>	NA	0.0183	0.018	0.0
Strain Madness 3	GCA_000015425	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
	GCA_000020225	<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	NA	NA	0.8699	0.8573	1.2136
	GCA_000008665	<i>Archaeoglobus fulgidus</i>	NA	NA	0.9157	0.9025	0.73
	GCA_000008005	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0

GCA_000011065	<i>Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron</i>	NA	NA	0.7325	0.722	0.4562
GCA_000010425	<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000195675	<i>Bordetella pertussis</i>	<i>Bordetella bronchiseptica</i>	NA	0.9157	0.9025	0.9125
GCA_000022325	<i>Caldicellulosiruptor bescii</i>	NA	NA	0.2253	0.222	0.2245
GCA_000016545	<i>Caldicellulosiruptor saccharolyticus</i>	NA	NA	0.9523	0.9386	1.4235
GCA_000015985	<i>Cereibacter A</i>	<i>Cereibacter sphaeroides</i>	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000006985	<i>Chlorobaculum tepidum</i>	NA	NA	0.1886	0.1859	0.4708
GCA_000020465	<i>Chlorobium limicola</i>	NA	NA	2.3075	2.2742	1.3797
GCA_000015125	<i>Chlorobium phaeobacteroides</i>	NA	NA	0.7783	0.7671	0.7756
GCA_000016085	<i>Chlorobium phaeovibrioides</i>	NA	NA	0.9157	0.9025	1.3687
GCA_000018865	<i>Chloroflexus aurantiacus</i>	NA	NA	0.3846	0.379	0.1916
GCA_000767745	<i>Clostridium beijerinckii</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000231215	<i>Cutibacterium acnes</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000008565	<i>Deinococcus radiodurans</i>	NA	NA	0.7325	0.7931	0.5475
GCA_000243155	<i>Desulfotobacterium dehalogenans</i>	NA	NA	0.0055	0.0054	0.0
GCA_002952055	<i>Desulfobulbus oralis</i>	NA	NA	7.3253	7.2196	3.65
GCA_000023225	<i>Desulfomicrobium baculatum</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0	0.0547
GCA_000189295	<i>Desulfovibrio mercurii</i>	NA	NA	0.0733	0.0722	0.0456
GCA_000156375	<i>Desulfovibrio piger</i>	NA	NA	4.5783	4.5123	6.8437

GCA_000021645	<i>Dictyoglomus turgidum</i>	NA	NA	0.4578	0.4512	0.365
GCA_000172575	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	NA	NA	0.1831	0.2516	0.365
GCA_000005845	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_003019295	<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	NA	NA	2.1976	2.1659	1.095
GCA_000010305	<i>Gemmatimonas aurantiaca</i>	NA	NA	4.0289	3.9708	4.015
GCA_000020725	<i>Geobacter bemidjiensis</i>	NA	NA	0.0055	0.0054	0.0
GCA_000007985	<i>Geobacter sulfurreducens</i>	NA	NA	0.8058	0.7942	0.1405
GCA_000006805	<i>Halobacterium salinarum</i>	NA	NA	1.8313	1.8049	1.825
GCA_000025685	<i>Haloferax volcanii</i>	NA	NA	0.0494	0.0487	0.0493
GCA_000008525	<i>Helicobacter pylori</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000018565	<i>Herpetosiphon aurantiacus</i>	NA	NA	4.0289	3.9708	6.4239
GCA_000020785	<i>Hydrogenobaculum</i> sp.	<i>Hydrogenobaculum</i> sp. Y04AAS1	NA	0.9157	0.9025	0.73
GCA_000017945	<i>Ignicoccus hospitalis</i>	NA	NA	1.3277	1.3086	1.9838
GCA_001481685	<i>Ignicoccus islandicus</i>	NA	NA	0.5494	0.5415	1.3687
GCA_000014425	<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000019785	<i>Leptothrix cholodnii</i>	NA	NA	0.0879	0.0866	0.0
GCA_001639275	<i>Methanobrevibacter oralis</i>	NA	NA	0.586	0.5776	0.0
GCA_000091665	<i>Methanocaldococcus jannaschii</i>	NA	NA	3.5345	3.4835	7.0444
GCA_000016125	<i>Methanococcus maripaludis</i>	NA	NA	0.7508	0.74	0.7482
GCA_000011585	<i>Methanococcus maripaludis</i>	NA	NA	0.2747	0.2707	0.1825
GCA_000308215	<i>Methanomassiliicoccus luminyensis</i>	NA	NA	0.0549	0.0541	0.0

GCA_000328665	<i>Methanomethylovorans hollandica</i>	NA	NA	0.0458	0.0451	0.0
GCA_000007185	<i>Methanopyrus kandleri</i>	NA	NA	0.1282	0.1263	0.1606
GCA_000007345	<i>Methanosarcina acetivorans</i>	NA	NA	0.3663	0.361	0.365
GCA_000166095	<i>Methanothermus fervidus</i>	NA	NA	3.2048	3.1586	2.555
GCA_000018265	<i>Micromonospora arenicola</i>	<i>Salinispora arenicola</i>	NA	0.8131	0.8014	0.657
GCA_000016425	<i>Micromonospora tropica</i>	<i>Salinispora tropica</i>	NA	0.9157	0.9025	0.73
GCA_000008085	<i>Nanoarchaeum equitans</i>	NA	NA	0.1685	0.1661	0.1113
GCA_000008805	<i>Neisseria meningitidis</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000195755	<i>Nitratidesulfovibrio vulgaris</i>	NA	NA	0.0366	0.0361	0.073
GCA_000009145	<i>Nitrosomonas europaea</i>	NA	NA	5.7504	5.6674	2.8652
GCA_000013645	<i>Paraburkholderia xenovorans</i>	NA	NA	2.0145	1.9854	1.0037
GCA_000154225	<i>Pauljensenia odontolyticus</i>	<i>Schaalia dentiphila</i>	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000020645	<i>Pelodictyon phaeoclathratiforme</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0	0.1131
GCA_000021565	<i>Persephonella marina</i>	NA	NA	2.0035	1.9746	1.095
GCA_000012825	<i>Phocaeicola vulgatus</i>	NA	NA	0.8717	0.9298	2.6061
GCA_000010505	<i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i>	NA	NA	1.8387	1.887	3.6646
GCA_002563335	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_931907645	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	NA	<i>Pseudomonas marginalis</i>	2.747	2.7074	0.9125
GCA_000007565	<i>Pseudomonas putida</i>	NA	NA	3.2964	3.2488	2.6645
GCA_000007225	<i>Pyrobaculum aerophilum</i>	NA	NA	0.1831	0.1805	0.0912

GCA_000016385	<i>Pyrobaculum arsenaticum</i>	NA	NA	0.0366	0.0361	0.0
GCA_000015805	<i>Pyrobaculum calidifontis</i>	NA	NA	1.8313	1.8049	0.365
GCA_000007305	<i>Pyrococcus furiosus</i>	NA	NA	0.2747	0.2707	0.0
GCA_000011105	<i>Pyrococcus horikoshii</i>	NA	NA	3.6627	3.6098	4.5625
GCA_000196115	<i>Rhodopirellula baltica</i>	NA	NA	3.388	3.3391	2.0257
GCA_000011965	<i>Ruegeria pomeroyi</i>	NA	NA	0.1099	0.1083	0.0
GCA_000015865	<i>Ruminiclostridium thermocellum</i>	<i>Acetivibrio thermocellus</i>	NA	0.3718	0.3664	0.2226
GCA_000017325	<i>Shewanella baltica</i>	NA	NA	2.5932	2.5558	3.4456
GCA_000021665	<i>Shewanella baltica</i>	NA	NA	4.8897	4.8191	5.8472
GCA_000016065	<i>Shewanella loihica</i>	NA	NA	0.9157	0.9025	1.2775
GCA_000013465	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000007645	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000007265	<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000817065	<i>Streptococcus mutans</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0722	0.0
GCA_000020325	<i>Sulfurihydrogenibium sp.</i>	<i>Sulfurihydrogenibium sp. YO3AOP1</i>	NA	0.4578	0.4512	0.365
GCA_000011205	<i>Sulfurisphaera tokodaii</i>	NA	NA	0.0733	0.0722	0.073
GCA_000019085	<i>Thermoanaerobacter pseudethanolicus</i>	NA	<i>Thermoanaerobacter brockii</i>	2.1097	2.0793	1.5768
GCA_000019625	<i>Thermotoga maritima</i>	<i>Thermotoga sp. RQ2</i>	NA	0.0	0.0	4.1975
GCA_000018945	<i>Thermotoga neapolitana</i>	NA	NA	1.0896	1.0739	2.1717
GCA_000016785	<i>Thermotoga petrophila</i>	NA	NA	4.56	4.4942	0.0
GCA_000008185	<i>Treponema denticola</i>	NA	NA	1.2966	1.2779	1.6151
GCA_000009705	<i>Trichormus sp.</i>	<i>Nostoc sp. PCC 7120 = FACHB-418</i>	NA	3.5528	3.5015	5.3107

	GCA_000196135	<i>Wolinella succinogenes</i>	NA	NA	0.4981	0.4909	0.4143
	GCA_000007105	<i>Zymomonas mobilis</i>	NA	NA	0.0	0.0	0.0365

332 Table S5.2: Species information of the ten DMCs. The first column denotes the DMC name. The second column shows the NCBI's assembly accession of the species in the DMCs. The third
333 column represents the original species name, while the fourth and fifth columns represent the updated species name as explained under 5.1.5 Update ground truth (NA means the species
334 name was not updated). The last column shows the relative abundance (%) of the present species in the DMC(s).

335 Table S5.3

	DMC	#Sequences	Yield	AvgQual	AvgLen	N50
Raw	Zymo D6300	3,491,078	14,007,156,825	8.33	4,012.3	5,213
	Zymo D6310	3,667,007	16,032,264,247	7.96	4,372	5,290
	Zymo D6322	8,851,918	31,995,546,765	13.56	3,614.5	13,837
	Zymo D6331	5,757,345	28,443,158,238	13.65	4,940.3	5,913
	Zymo D6332	1,140,052	7,530,532,667	20.57	6,605.4	8,598
	Bei Resources HM-276D	11,610,183	35,578,375,166	8.68	3,064.4	6,828
	Bei Resources HM-277D	18,254,839	72,312,638,112	10.06	3,961.3	7,857
	Strain madness 1	696,944	3,125,920,499	10.62	4,485.2	6,086
	Strain madness 2	831,802	3,690,876,744	10.63	4,437.2	6,057
	Strain madness 3	791,715	3,412,736,796	10.6	4,310.6	5,788
Filtered	Zymo D6300	688,666	3,184,351,336	10.38	4,623.9	5,397
	Zymo D6310	407,843	1,934,530,540	10.31	4,743.3	5,442
	Zymo D6322	4,401,162	28,272,769,892	13.95	6,423.9	15,966
	Zymo D6331	5,757,345	28,443,158,238	13.65	4,940.3	5,913
	Zymo D6332	1,076,408	7,468,390,687	20.84	6,938.3	8,627
	Bei Resources HM-276D	2,163,256	11,018,419,575	10.52	5,093.4	8,572
	Bei Resources HM-277D	7,002,956	37,506,985,368	11.71	5,355.9	8,560
	Strain madness 1	485,802	2,428,082,669	11.2	4,998.1	6,182
	Strain madness 2	579,446	2,875,480,429	11.2	4,962.5	6,157
	Strain madness 3	553,288	2,647,336,371	11.17	4,784.7	5,882

336 Table S5.3: Sequence statistics of the DMCs before and after filtering. The first column denotes before (raw) and after
337 (filtered) filtering. The second column shows the DMC name. The third, the fourth, the fifth, the sixth and seventh columns
338 denote the number of sequences, the number of bases, their average Phred score, average length and N50, respectively.

	Probiotic	#Sequences	Yield	AvgQual	AvgLen	N50
Raw	PROBIOTIC1	3,541,293	19,215,502,743	11.72	5,426.1	12,928
	PROBIOTIC2	5,814,033	12,001,290,346	12.28	2,064.2	3,454
	PROBIOTIC3	1,375,061	2,356,782,880	12.97	1,713.9	2,463
	PROBIOTIC4	4,527,675	16,019,595,242	12.9	3,538.2	4,519
	PROBIOTIC5	751,547	2,490,777,975	12.71	3,314.2	4,423
	PROBIOTIC6	1,089,396	4,019,809,690	13.7	3,689.9	6,423
	PROBIOTIC7	1,063,709	2,628,339,571	12.04	2,470.9	3,982
	PROBIOTIC8	4,002,421	11,231,916,704	14.1	2,806.3	3,743
	PROBIOTIC9	4,150,274	9,860,786,912	13.47	2,375.9	3,331
	PROBIOTIC10	5,676,447	7,758,362,901	12.95	1,366.8	2,373
Filtered	PROBIOTIC1	2,074,105	14,347,056,176	16.17	6,917.2	13,060
	PROBIOTIC2	2,718,591	8,847,033,162	16.05	3,254.3	3,872
	PROBIOTIC3	745,755	1,780,800,204	17.84	2,387.9	2,646
	PROBIOTIC4	3,275,806	13,054,825,270	17.41	3,985.2	4,560
	PROBIOTIC5	540,226	2,091,326,685	17.27	3,871.2	4,444
	PROBIOTIC6	742,646	3,496,515,149	17.56	4,708.2	6,540
	PROBIOTIC7	581,947	1,970,407,791	16.69	3,385.9	4,246
	PROBIOTIC8	2,852,193	9,608,104,802	18.14	3,368.7	3,834
	PROBIOTIC9	2,610,428	8,020,864,325	17.6	3,072.6	3,474
	PROBIOTIC10	1,961,931	5,215,493,143	17.15	2,658.3	3,119

340 Table S5.4: Sequence statistics of the probiotic-derived mock communities before and after filtering. The first column
 341 denotes before (raw) and after (filtered) filtering. The second column shows the probiotic-derived mock community name.
 342 The third, the fourth, the fifth, the sixth and seventh columns denote the number of sequences, the number of bases, their
 343 average Phred score, average length and N50, respectively.

344

345 Table S5.5

Sample Yield	Filter setting	Template ID (%)	Template Coverage (%)	Similarity (%)
200M	Maximum F1	6.60	7.11	95.84
	FDR 15%	0.00	0.00	0.00
	FDR 10%	0.10	0.16	95.13
	FDR 5%	1.72	1.85	94.78
	FDR 1%	8.11	8.65	94.71
500M	Maximum F1	2.67	2.84	94.81
	FDR 15%	0.07	0.12	81.95
	FDR 10%	0.15	0.60	93.60
	FDR 5%	1.97	2.13	93.32
	FDR 1%	10.88	13.44	93.46
1000M	Maximum F1	3.14	3.39	93.18
	FDR 15%	1.06	1.15	95.50
	FDR 10%	1.46	1.56	94.20
	FDR 5%	2.39	2.90	84.48
	FDR 1%	12.78	15.21	88.06
1500M	Maximum F1	11.16	12.99	95.66
	FDR 15%	1.18	1.27	94.14
	FDR 10%	2.05	2.27	95.48
	FDR 5%	2.59	2.81	94.10
	FDR 1%	13.71	14.96	93.39
2000M	Maximum F1	12.25	13.14	93.50
	FDR 15%	1.26	1.47	87.46
	FDR 10%	2.25	2.69	93.91
	FDR 5%	2.75	3.35	86.00
	FDR 1%	18.13	22.23	94.36

346 Table S5.5: Template ID values and its corresponding template coverage and similarity for our optimized pipeline. The first
347 and second column shows the sample yield and filter setting. The third, fourth and fifth column show the corresponding
348 template ID, along with its template coverage and similarity.

349

350 Table S5.6

Standard	No threshold	200M	NA
		500M	NA
		1000M	NA
		1500M	NA
		2000M	NA
	Maximum F1	200M	0.017
		500M	0.009
		1000M	0.016
		1500M	0.015
		2000M	0.016
	FDR 5%	200M	0.305
		500M	0.387
		1000M	0.386
		1500M	0.384
		2000M	0.387
Novel	No threshold	200M	NA
		500M	NA
		1000M	NA
		1500M	NA
		2000M	NA
	Maximum F1	200M	6.595
		500M	2.674
		1000M	3.135
		1500M	11.163
		2000M	12.252
	FDR 5%	200M	1.716
		500M	1.968
		1000M	2.390
		1500M	2.592
		2000M	2.745

351 Table S5.6: DMC filtering threshold used for Figure 2, Figure 4 and Figure S1. The first column shows the filter approach.

352 The second, third column and fourth lists the selection strategy, the sample yield and the used filter threshold,

353 respectively. For the standard approach, the filter threshold is based on the relative abundance, while to the novel
354 approach, the threshold is based on the Template ID.

355

Sample Yield	Filter setting	Template ID (%)
200M	Maximum F1	7.359
	FDR 15%	0.003
	FDR 10%	0.003
	FDR 5%	1.023
	FDR 1%	1.023
500M	Maximum F1	12.442
	FDR 15%	0.019
	FDR 10%	1.324
	FDR 5%	1.383
	FDR 1%	1.383
1000M	Maximum F1	17.258
	FDR 15%	1.405
	FDR 10%	1.57
	FDR 5%	1.60
	FDR 1%	1.60
1500M	Maximum F1	23.28
	FDR 15%	1.50
	FDR 10%	1.82
	FDR 5%	2.44
	FDR 1%	2.44
2000M	Maximum F1	26.02
	FDR 15%	1.50
	FDR 10%	1.88
	FDR 5%	3.59
	FDR 1%	3.59

357 Table S5.7: PDMC filtering threshold used for Figure S7B. The first and second column shows the sample yield and filter
358 setting. The third column shows the corresponding template ID.

359

Sample name	Species name	Species name on 02/2023	Changed species name
PROBIOTIC1	<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium bifidum</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	NA	NA
PROBIOTIC2	<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus</i>	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus paracasei</i>	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i>	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium breve</i>	NA	NA
PROBIOTIC3	<i>Lactobacillus crispatus</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus brevis</i>	<i>Levilactobacillus brevis</i>	NA
PROBIOTIC4	<i>Lactobacillus reuteri</i>	<i>Limosilactobacillus reuteri</i>	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus</i>	NA
PROBIOTIC5	<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	NA	NA
PROBIOTIC6	<i>Lactiplantibacillus pentosus</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i>	NA	NA
PROBIOTIC7	<i>Streptococcus salivarius</i>	NA	NA
PROBIOTIC8	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium bifidum</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium breve</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium infantis</i>	<i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus delbrueckii</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus casei</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus casei</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus paracasei</i>
	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i>	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus</i>	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus salivarius</i>	<i>Ligilactobacillus salivarius</i>	NA
	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i>	NA	NA
PROBIOTIC9	<i>Bifidobacterium breve</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium infantis</i>	<i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	NA
	<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus</i>	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i>	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>	<i>Lacticaseibacillus paracasei</i>	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus bulgaricus</i>	<i>Lactobacillus delbrueckii</i>	NA
PROBIOTIC10	<i>Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Pediococcus acidilactici</i>	NA	NA

	<i>Lacticaseibacillus casei</i>	NA	<i>Lacticaseibacillus paracasei</i>
	<i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Bifidobacterium breve</i>	NA	NA
	<i>Lactococcus lactis subsp. lactis</i>	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	NA

361 Table S5.8: Species information of the ten probiotic-derived mock communities. The first column denotes the probiotic
362 name The second column represents the original species name based on the product label, while the fourth column
363 represents the updated species name as explained under 5.1.5 Update ground truth (NA means the species name was not
364 updated).

365

Standard	No threshold	200M	NA
		500M	NA
		1000M	NA
		1500M	NA
		2000M	NA
	Maximum F1	200M	2.10
		500M	2.10
		1000M	2.04
		1500M	2.05
		2000M	2.03
	FDR 5%	200M	0.03
		500M	0.03
		1000M	0.04
		1500M	0.04
		2000M	0.04
Novel	No threshold	200M	NA
		500M	NA
		1000M	NA
		1500M	NA
		2000M	NA
	Maximum F1	200M	7.36
		500M	12.44
		1000M	17.26
		1500M	23.29
		2000M	26.02
	FDR 5%	200M	1.02
		500M	1.38
		1000M	1.60
		1500M	2.44
		2000M	3.59

367 Table S5.9: PDMC filtering threshold used for Figure S3. The first column shows the filter approach. The second, third
368 column and fourth lists the selection strategy, the sample yield and the used filter threshold, respectively. For the standard

369 approach, the filter threshold is based on the relative abundance, while to the novel approach, the threshold is based on
370 the Template ID.

371

372 5.3. Figures

373 Figure S5.1

374

375 Figure S5.1: Number of TPs, FPs and FNs of the standard and novel approaches applied to the DMCs. Rows show the number of TPs, FPs, and FNs, while columns represent the three selection
376 strategies: no thresholds applied, maximum F1 score, and FDR5. The x-axis shows the five sample yields, whereas the y-axis shows the respective metric values expressed as boxplots. Blue and
377 orange boxplots indicate the performance for the standard and novel approaches, respectively, with solid and dotted lines indicating the median and mean of each boxplot. The used filter
378 thresholds are shown in Table S5.6.

379

380 Figure S5.2

	PROBIOTIC 1	PROBIOTIC 2	PROBIOTIC 3	PROBIOTIC 4	PROBIOTIC 5	PROBIOTIC 6	PROBIOTIC 7	PROBIOTIC 8	PROBIOTIC 9	PROBIOTIC 10
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>					Dark Blue					
<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>										
<i>Bacillus paralicheniformis</i>										
<i>Bacillus siamensis</i>										
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>								Dark Blue		
<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>										
<i>Bifidobacterium animalis</i>										
<i>Bifidobacterium bifidum</i>	Dark Blue							Dark Blue		
<i>Bifidobacterium breve</i>	Light Blue	Dark Blue						Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
<i>Bifidobacterium longum</i>	Dark Blue	Dark Blue						Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
<i>Lactocaseibacillus casei</i>								Hatched		Hatched
<i>Lactocaseibacillus paracasei</i>		Dark Blue						Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
<i>Lactocaseibacillus rhamnosus</i>		Dark Blue		Dark Blue				Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
<i>Lactiplantibacillus paraplantarum</i>						Light Blue				
<i>Lactiplantibacillus pentosus</i>						Dark Blue				
<i>Lactiplantibacillus plantarum</i>		Dark Blue				Dark Blue		Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i>		Dark Blue						Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
<i>Lactobacillus amylovorus</i>			Light Blue							
<i>Lactobacillus crispatus</i>			Dark Blue					Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
<i>Lactobacillus delbrueckii</i>								Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i>	Hatched								Hatched	
<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>								Dark Blue		Dark Blue
<i>Lactobacillus paragasseri</i>	Dark Blue									
<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>								Dark Blue		Dark Blue
<i>Levilactobacillus brevis</i>			Dark Blue							
<i>Ligilactobacillus salivarius</i>								Dark Blue		
<i>Limosilactobacillus reuteri</i>				Dark Blue						
<i>Pediococcus acidilactici</i>										Dark Blue
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>										
<i>Streptococcus infantarius</i>										
<i>Streptococcus salivarius</i>							Dark Blue			
<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i>							Light Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue	Dark Blue
<i>Streptococcus vestibularis</i>							Light Blue			
<i>Weizmannia coagulans</i>										

381

382 Figure S5.2: MetaCARP analysis of the ten probiotic-derived mock communities. Rows show the species names and columns show the probiotic-derived mock community names. A cell filled
 383 with dark blue means a high confidence detection with MetaCARP while a light blue means a low confidence detection. Hatched cells are expected species based on the product label (i.e.,
 384 species in the ground truth).

385

386 Figure S5.3

387

388 Figure S5.3: Precision, recall, and F1 scores of the standard and novel approaches applied to the PDMCs. Rows show precision, recall, and F1 scores, while columns represent the three
 389 selection strategies: no thresholds applied, maximum F1 score, and FDR5. The x-axis shows the five sample yields, whereas the y-axis shows the respective metric values of the ten probiotic
 390 samples expressed as boxplots. Blue and orange boxplots indicate the performance for the standard and novel approaches, respectively, with solid and dotted lines indicating the median and
 391 mean of each boxplot. Note that the used thresholds were based on the PDMCs and not the ones from the DMCs. The used filter thresholds are shown in Table S5.9.

392 Figure S5.4

393

394 Figure S5.4: Effects of sequencing yield on TPs, FPs and FNs for the novel approach applied to the probiotic-derived mock communities. (A) Number of TPs, FPs and FNs for all ten probiotic-
 395 derived mock communities using the novel approach without filtering. The x-axis shows the five different yields, while the y-axis shows the counts of TPs (green bars), FPs (red bars), and FNs
 396 (blue bars). (B) Template IDs of TPs and FPs for all ten probiotic-derived mock communities using the novel approach without filtering. The x-axis shows the five different yields, while the y-axis
 397 shows the template ID. Green and red boxplots indicate TPs and FPs, respectively, with a solid line indicating the median. FNs are not shown as they all have a template ID of 0%.

398 Figure S5.5

399

400 Figure S5.5: Effects of DMC-derived template ID filtering for different selection strategies across different sequencing yields applied to the probiotic-derived mock communities. Each subplot
401 represents the six different selection strategies. The x-axis represents the different sequencing yields, while the y-axis shows the value (%) of the performance metrics and associated DMC-
402 derived template ID thresholds (see also Figure 4). Blue, orange, green and red boxplots indicate the precision, recall, F1 and template ID threshold of all ten probiotic-derived mock communities.

403 Figure S5.6

404

405 Figure S5.6: Template ID and theoretical relative abundance of all TPs in the ten DMCs at yield 2000M. The x-axis shows the theoretical relative abundance (%), while the y-axis shows the
406 template ID (%). Green markers represent the TPs.

407

408

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